

raisd

Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced

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Recommendations on the adoption of a TAIS-oriented approach

- Deliverable 3.5 -

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<i>About RAISD</i>	
<i>Call (part) identifier</i>	<i>H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2018</i>
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<p><i>Forced displacement crises overcome societies and institutions all over the world. Pushed by the urgencies rather than events, solutions are frequently reactive, partial, and disregard some groups. The project 'Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced' (RAISD) aims at identifying highly Vulnerable Groups (VG) among these forcibly displaced people, analysing their specific needs, and finding suitable practices to address them. The concept of 'vulnerability context' considers the interplay between the features of these persons and their hosting communities, their interactions and experiences, and how different solutions for attention and inclusion affect them. As a result of this work, a methodology to carry out these studies will be developed. These goals are aligned with the call. They pursue characterizing these migrations and developing suitable aid strategies for them. The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) frames the project. It proposes that all actors (including civil society) co-design actions, transversely integrates the gender perspective, and supports sustainability. Our research strategy will be based on methodological triangulation (i.e. the combined application of several methodologies). We will implement it through a specific participatory action research approach to fulfil the aim of undertaking advocacy-focused research, grounded in human rights and socio-ecological models. The team will work as a network of units in countries along migration routes. The units will promote the VG people' involvement, so they can speak with their own voices, gather information, and test practices. Work will rely on a tight integration of Social and Computer Sciences research. Automated learning and data mining will help to provide evidence-based recommendations, reducing a priori biases. A software tool will support collaboration, continuing previous H2020- funded RRI work.</i></p>	

The sole responsibility of this publication lies with the author.

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Glossary

ARU	Action Research Unit
AUCL	ALL YOU CAN LEARN, acronym Italian TAIS
AU	Anadolu University
BIP	Beneficiaries of International Protection
EC	European Commission
FDP	Forcibly Displaced People / Person
HVG	Highly Vulnerable Group
LIU	Lebanese International University
Menedék	Hungarian Association for Migrants
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PRSF	Psychosocial Refugee Support Forum
RAISD	Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
RSS	Refugee Support System
TAIS	Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategy
UCM	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
UH	University of Helsinki
VC	Vulnerability Context
VG	Vulnerable Group
WP	Work Package
YU	Yarmouk University

Executive Summary

This document provides a Catalogue of actor-oriented recommendations for the effective implementation of the TAIS (Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies) oriented approaches, tailored to specific Vulnerable Groups in different Vulnerability Contexts depending on the host community or country where the TAIS has been piloted. Indeed, each TAIS was tailored to fit the local environment and address a given vulnerability context; therefore, the activities are diverse to respond to the specific needs of the vulnerable individuals:

- The [Spanish TAIS](#) consists of a training and counselling program for self-employment for Sub-Saharan women seeking international protection, whose application has been accepted, rejected or is pending.
- The [Italian TAIS](#) "ALL you can LEARN" involved Forcibly Displaced Women living and/or exposed to highly vulnerable situations and conditions, victims of human trafficking currently living in Sicily, originally from Ivory Coast, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Somalia, Comoros and Tunisia.
- The [Finnish TAIS](#) was designed in the form of two parallel pilot activities. The multilingual online forum's target group was young asylum-seeking men with few social connections with particularly Finnish-speaking men, whereas the other was designed to develop already existing child-care services in the asylum seekers' reception centres for families living there.
- The [Hungarian TAIS](#) had the objective was to pilot a trajectory monitoring toolbox for social workers working with refugees to recognise and assess the context of their vulnerability.
- The [Turkish TAIS](#) was designed to focus on the monitoring of social integration of vulnerable FDPs through a series of workshops to enhance the capacities and awareness for various stakeholders.
- The [Jordanian TAIS](#) aimed to provide psychological support for refugees together with online trainings about financial, legal and health awareness.
- The [Lebanese TAIS](#) promoted health awareness among Syrian refugees living in camps. The COVID-19 emergency made it necessary to combine simple awareness-raising activities with a more strategic approach via trainings focusing on social and emotional well-being.

The TAIS Recommendations have also been drafted by the national [Action-Research Units](#) ([Spain](#), [Italy](#), [Finland](#), [Hungary](#), [Turkey](#), [Jordan](#) and [Lebanon](#)) consulting with the researchers, service providers and beneficiaries of the activities - the Forcible Displaced themselves. Their recommendations vary in scope and inclusion needs, addressing:

- World level, European and International Institutions and Agencies (EC, UNHCR, IOM).
- Country level (government, regional, local authorities and institutions).
- Host community level (ARU members/inclusion strategy implementers)
- Highly Vulnerable People among the Forcibly Displaced

Ultimately these Recommendations support the validation of existing practices and provide rationales for the improvement in future implementations of such strategies regarding the care of vulnerable groups: WHY 'Needs and problem identification', WHAT 'needs to be improved or changed', HOW 'can it be improved?' to extend the innovative attention and inclusion strategy to other Vulnerable Groups and different Vulnerability Context and to further involve potential adopters of the TAIS methodologies, materials, products, services.

Each Partner is the sole responsible for the draft of the specific country related TAIS Recommendations.

Refuge of power: Sub-Saharan women's entrepreneurship and coaching program

After conducting interviews with experts and vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced, as well as organizing 7 meetings with 36 different organisations representing the quintuple helix of RRI, we decided that one of the most vulnerable groups in Spain was the one formed by Sub-Saharan women, and that employability was among their main difficulties. Therefore, the Spanish ARU decided to co-design the following TAIS: Refuge of power: Sub-Saharan women's entrepreneurship and coaching program.

The aim of the TAIS is to develop competences to promote the socioeconomic inclusion of sub-Saharan refugee women or applicants for international protection in Spain as well as fostering the beneficiaries' self-reliance, autonomy and general level of work market competence.

The program focuses on different skills and capacities (digital, emotional, communication, leadership, management and entrepreneurship) that have been selected to form part of the program, then validated by ARU members and some potential beneficiaries in the consultation processes. These skills also stand out for having a high value for the job market, and the professional and personal development of the beneficiaries.

The Spanish TAIS translates into a very flexible social intervention process, highly adaptable to the needs and demands of the participants and the Covid19 context. The target women have been highly engaged and form an active group in the design, development, and evaluation of the practices.

The TAIS is a training and support process with a twofold course of action:

1. In terms of entrepreneurship, so that the beneficiaries are trained to be able to create a collective productive project (cooperative).
2. Strengthening of abilities and competences, preparing the beneficiaries for greater employability and supporting their professional growth.

The group of final beneficiaries is heterogeneous in terms of age, family situation, education, digital skills, work, and personal experiences.

Different organisations and experts have participated in the program. Among them, we must highlight the key role of Nantik Lum (<https://nantiklum.org/?lang=en>) and PAZ.AI (<https://www.paz.ai/>) and well as the highly engaged social worker.

Spanish TAIS Testimonies <https://raisd-h2020.eu/research/aru/spain/>

Spanish Good Practices <https://raisd-h2020.eu/media/d5.1-potential-gps-es.pdf>

Recommendations to improve policies and practices regarding the care of vulnerable groups

In Spain, the policies and practices regarding the care of vulnerable groups among FDP are often partial, fragmented or overlapping, leaving important gaps in terms of the needs and requirements of the migrants. Therefore, we would recommend augmented collaboration among organisations at all levels, among NGOs and humanitarian aid agencies themselves and between the two collectives. Organisations and administrations should open up, listen to each other and collaborate in the creation of policies and strategies and also, focus on adjusting the programs into the real needs of FDP, with coherent offers that do not overlap and cover the core needs, offering variety instead of competing. This could be possible including the FDP in the design, implementation, and evaluation of the programs, giving them voice and position in the committees, work groups and decision-making organs.

In general terms, the needs of FDP and the potential benefits for them should be the starting point for any planning of social intervention programs, and these should be always placed above the organisation's goals, avoiding paternalistic and patronising approaches. This would be possible if FDP's active voices were heard and considered. A more democratic governance and decision-making process is necessary to give effective answers and respond to FDP needs in terms of integration and attention. This also means listening to other stakeholders' ideas, those that are normally outside these kinds of processes related to forced migration -such as companies, citizens, and the sector of education- but can contribute with ideas, funding possibilities, volunteers, etc.

Also, more attention should be paid to the collaborative and inclusive evaluation of the programs, embedding both the process and outcome perspectives to guarantee they respond to the real needs of FDP, tailored to the characteristics of different beneficiary groups. Sometimes, deficient communication strategies hinder reaching the neediest of the potential beneficiaries. To improve the communication and select the right messages and channels, and get to the right people, FDP should be listened to when making communication strategies.

The attention and inclusion processes need to dedicate sufficient time to prepare the final beneficiaries for their phase of real emancipation. On many occasions, real and psychological dependence can be unintentionally generated by assisting organisations. To avoid this, programs that seek greater autonomy and generate support networks among the FDP themselves and with host communities would be of great value, considering also adequate language training and improving employability.

Regarding programs that promote employment, there are still policies to improve. Social workers lack the time, and sometimes the necessary training. So, the job opportunities offered to FDP are often based on stereotypes rather than on the previous training and professional experience of beneficiaries.

Extending the innovative attention and inclusion strategy to other Vulnerable Groups and different Vulnerability Context

Based on our TAIS experience, fine tailoring of contents and approaches is required when adjusting even the already defined and pre-tested strategies to the precise profile and mindsets of the participants. There is always a distance between the initial plans and the coming up with the expectations, reaching a satisfactory level of motivation, and responding to the real needs and desires of the beneficiary groups. In our opinion and based on the results of the TAIS process and outcome evaluations by service providers, beneficiaries and ARU members, the program is valuable and transferable to other vulnerable groups, not necessarily forcibly displaced people. This kind of training and mentoring that works in the employability and entrepreneurship of groups in risk of social inclusion could also be adapted to other types of underprivileged social groups, including Romanies or migrants from developing or emerging countries. In any case, the program would need a very detailed readjustment: listening to the new types of beneficiaries, finding the right persons and organisations with the necessary expertise to provide the services, fitting the program and timetables to the possibilities of the target groups, etc.

In the organising team and ARU members' opinion, the TAIS structure, the reiterative evaluation system and the core contents, as well as the working methodology, a participatory one with different stakeholders including FDP, is highly transferable and useful in other contexts when working with vulnerable small groups. Also, the lessons learned would give us important insights on how to better tailor our attention and inclusion strategies.

ARU members have provided a series of examples of groups that could also benefit from this TAIS:

- Trans women or women victims of gender violence. Helping these women to become part of society again, solve different problems (economic, work, vulnerability, health...). The idea is to create self-help groups with organisational support and generate networks.
- People with mental illness, who suffer isolation and loneliness.
- People who have suffered trauma and who have to face the labour market, as they need more support.
- Male FDP. Many of them find themselves alone living in great isolation, their environment has high expectations, and they lack a network. Especially interesting for men of sub-Saharan, Syrian or Afghan origin.
- Migrants who could be regularised due to social roots with an entrepreneurship project. This TAIS could serve for that process by accompanying them in the creation of that feasibility project.
- In Spain the legislation for unaccompanied migrant minors has changed, now they could benefit from this kind of TAIS program.
- Victims of human trafficking processes who are going to apply for international protection.
- Online entrepreneurship can also be of great interest to the population living in rural settings, whether they are migrants displaced to those areas or non-migrants settled there.
- Online entrepreneurship could make work easier for displaced people if they must move to other places.
- Employability is not a goal for displaced people who are in transit and have not yet reached their final destinations. But this TAIS is not only a training program for employment or self-employment, but it is also a space for connection and collective learning, of shared needs among these people.
- It could also be applied to start a business in other countries apart from Spain.

Regarding other contexts for entrepreneurship:

- In Spain the legal situation is changing so that a company can be established with much less capital than previously.

The conditions and characteristics for entrepreneurship vary greatly from one country to another. Possibly, it can be better applied in other countries where starting a business is easier than in Spain. However, it is not the same inclusion process in other countries, since it is not only necessary to take into consideration the normative part, but also the social part. Considering this social part, the TAIS may not be as easily applicable in other countries, although it is easier to undertake a new business.

Potential adopters of the TAIS methodology, materials, products, services

The results of our TAIS could be useful for diverse organisations working with FDP, above all NGOs, but also some large humanitarian agencies and administrations at diverse levels could adopt some of the collaborative and RRI responsive working methods. We expect our materials and resources to be very useful for other projects and initiatives working in similar issues and settings, to researchers specialising in vulnerable groups, to NGOs and agencies planning programs, to EC policy makers on forced migration and to universities and research groups on migration issues. Also, the RAISD Observatory on Forced Migration might implant future strategies (in case it gets funding) based on our current TAIS and the lessons learned.

It is a work methodology adaptable to other contexts. The TAIS methodology would adapt very well to people who have suffered trauma in their migration process. The job market is sometimes too aggressive for them, and they need more tailored support. Forced migrants tend to find themselves alone and helpless in Spain.

This TAIS can also serve as a boost to the support network of the displaced people themselves, generating alternative networks. When these people leave the system or the application for international protection is rejected, they remain outside the system. Programs like the TAIS can help them and provide them with a feeling of belonging.

Micro segmentation is a good way to start initiatives and really understand people's needs. In addition, the methodology developed by RAISD and applied in the TAISs incorporates the participation of different stakeholders, including FDP, and continuous evaluation. The TAIS methodology can be replicated in any intervention of this type with vulnerable beneficiaries, because vulnerability isolates people and tailored programs help them to feel they are recovering their lives.

The following potential adopters have been considered in an ARU meeting:

- NGOs that work with migrants, but also other organisations that work with vulnerable groups, such as national or regional organisations, city councils, etc.
- Organisations that work with women victims of gender violence.
- Any organisation that works with FDP, because the methodology works as a process of continuous diagnosis, evaluation, and adaptation. Spanish ARU members think that organisations of all levels should network in this way.
- Organisations that work in employment and entrepreneurship.
- The adoption of Action Research and RRI would be very beneficial for all aspects of social intervention programs.

The ARU members think that the organisations that serve migrants could apply this TAIS to different vulnerable groups, as long as the cost reduction is met. The TAIS pilot program has shown possibilities to replicate it in other vulnerable groups at a lower cost. So, the TAIS can be considered replicable.

The recommendations made by the Spanish ARU members are to keep the groups of beneficiaries small, since it would lose effectiveness in larger groups. It is also recommended to keep the training synchronous, since the level of concentration is higher in the beneficiaries. For the replication of the TAIS, recorded sessions could be used as long as there is a social worker trained in Action Research and RRI who can develop the mentoring and energise the group. Even the beneficiaries themselves, with the necessary time and training, could carry out part of the mentoring.

Include FDP in the design and decision-making process and measure the success of initiatives through processes and not just results

WHY

International migration policies and broad action plans to foster the integration and attention of FDP are often designed within expert teams, and even though they include NGOs and humanitarian aid agencies, forced migrants are not usually included in the design and decision-making process. Therefore, the power structure in these policies is vertical.

Although there is collaboration among international organisations and other actors (NGOs, administrations, and policy makers, etc.), it is necessary to generate more networks. International actors and local NGOs are very uneven in terms of decision-making power. Picturing FDP as victims gives room to paternalistic practices instead of strengthening them. Furthermore, through these behaviours, the re-victimization of forced migrants is exacerbated.

Additionally, the NGOs feel that the organisations that finance entities that work with migrants measure the success of their actions mainly considering quantitative and not qualitative outputs, so they do not consider how the social intervention initiatives really help the final beneficiaries on a personal and social level. This fact distorts the preparation of grant applications, because NGOs must commit to results that are not realistic in order to compete in these calls.

WHAT

FDP should be included in the design and planning process of international attention and inclusion policies and their voices should be heard in decision making. International organisations should promote a closer collaboration among international, national, regional, and local stakeholders. At this point, it is important to remember the importance of integrating civil society and the FDP themselves in the processes and work networks. Carefully listening to FDP and integrating their views in the strategic plans enables international organisations to design better tailored plans and policies that actually empower FDP.

Furthermore, institutions at global and European levels that finance organisations that work with migrants

Thus, FDP can become active stakeholders and become protagonists of the policies and strategies that affect their own future. More networks among international, national, regional, and local agents should be generated, also considering civil society and FDP.

Approaching the issues concerning forced migration integration from the point of view of the FDP themselves empowers FDP and avoids re-victimization. In this way, migrants would feel that they can regain their decision-making capacity in their own vital projects, increasing their autonomy. Furthermore, the proposals and programs would adequately respond to the needs of the final beneficiaries.

On the other hand, institutions at a global and European level that finance organisations that work with migrants and forced migrants must value how the initiatives help the final beneficiaries in their real lives, for example, to recover from the migration trauma; as well as consider the success of the social intervention initiatives as a process, avoiding evaluating only the quantitative results.

HOW

Forming committees and workgroups with FDP in the decision making and design process of inclusion policies and programs, from the very beginning until the end, including the evaluation phase. FDP should be included in the work groups. For this, it is advisable to apply the methodological principles of Responsible Research and Innovation, as well as Action Research to other areas of application beyond the pilot programs of research.

should assess the success of the initiatives considering the process and how the initiative actually helps the final beneficiaries, and not only the quantitative results. With this aim, some ARU members, especially NGOs, have mentioned that the evaluation criteria and the framework developed in RAISD project have provided them with ideas to be able to measure the success of their social interventions as processes and in a more holistic way.

These recommendations are also applicable to national and regional contexts.

UCM recommends to Spanish Country level (government, regional, local authorities and institutions).

Improve attention and inclusion strategies by involving national employment systems in attention and inclusion strategies and facilitating the homologation of official educational certificates

WHY

Due to lack of an open dialogue among the administration and organisations, some of the policies and strategies are overlapping, there are gaps in the programs that no organisation fills and, in some cases, instead of a collaborative approach, there can even be competition among entities in terms of reaching out for the groups of beneficiaries.

The NGOs have lost their ability to take a stance, although they are the ones who do a large part of the strategic action of inclusion and social care in Spain.

The experts participating in the Spanish ARU observe involuntary paternalistic and patronising approaches of the inclusion policies and programs that do not help to empower migrants, instead, they might create dependence.

Additionally, there are obstacles that affect other social groups in Spain, but that have a greater impact on forced migrants, such as unemployment or the fact that the processes of homologation of official educational certificates are long and expensive.

WHAT

It is necessary that the organisations at national, regional, and local level promote this type of initiatives that favour employability and self-employment and, in addition, that these organisations facilitate those other organisations can develop it.

In the case of especially vulnerable people among forced migrants, the processes of attention and inclusion are even longer and require more support. An example of this are their greater difficulties when accessing the labour market.

Also, to facilitate their access to the labour market and that their training and to make sure that their previous experience can be taken into account by employers,

highly vulnerable groups should not bear the financial costs of the homologation of official educational certificates. These procedures should be streamlined.

HOW

Creating committees and joining shared work groups among policy makers and organisations and co-designing solutions for a better integration of FDP. This way, overlapping programs and gaps in attention and inclusion plans can be detected and avoided.

Carefully listening to FDP and integrating their views in the strategic plans enable NGOs and local administrations to design better tailored plans and policies that actually empower FDP. To do this, some members of the Spanish ARU affirm that the methodology of RAISD project that combines Responsible Research and Innovation, Action-Research and socio-ecological models is an interesting starting point.

Involving national, regional, and local institutions in charge of promoting employment to consider initiatives like this TAIS in terms of professional growth and even entrepreneurship.

It is also necessary that the different governments give more support to the organisations so that they can develop this type of social intervention programs.

National, regional, and local organisations that finance organisations that work with migrants must value how the initiatives help the final beneficiaries to recover from the migration trauma, as well as consider the success of the social intervention initiatives as a process, avoiding evaluating only the quantitative results.

Finally, the processes of homologation of official educational certificates should be facilitated by the universities and defrayed by the state in case of especially vulnerable groups.

Consider deadlines and avoid stereotypes in attention and inclusion practices, trying to favour the associative fabric in the neighbourhoods including FDP

WHY

During the pandemic, it has been observed that many of the associations that have been able to give direct assistance to vulnerable groups within the FDP have been neighbourhood associations.

The Spanish ARU considers that the TAIS can be replicated thanks to the lessons learned, however, there are certain aspects that must be considered. For example, depending on the length of the TAIS, FDP may be left out of the program. The problem is due to the deadlines. Depending on their situation in the process, if these deadlines are not met, displaced persons may be left out of the protection system and have to leave the TAIS program.

In general terms, and referring to the employability programs that are currently being developed in Spain, there are very precarious professional sectors, such as cleaning and caring for the elderly, stereotypically associated with women and migrants.

Due to how training programs for FDP are currently evaluated, entities and trainers tend to focus only on complying with all the contents and objectives of the training programs -established a priori- and that are the same regardless of the characteristics of each group. Sometimes, due to reduced resources, time limits and poor evaluation strategies, program follow up is superficial or non-existent, and the knowledge on the actual outcomes and benefits for FDP is lacking.

WHAT

Organisations and trainers should not focus solely on complying with all the contents and objectives of the training program established a priori and offering the same regardless of the characteristics of each group. Institutions (NGOs, administration...) sometimes offer too many resources and training opportunities for refugees, but they do not apply a necessary follow-up to evaluate if the people who take these courses acquire the necessary skills to develop professionally. It would be necessary to carry out a monitoring activity to ensure if the courses are effective and really beneficial for refugees.

There is a need for a specific training of trainers, about the beneficiaries, their contexts, about the asylum

processes; and also, working on the awareness of the technical staff to improve social care provision.

It is important to generate processes that give rise to the creation of networks, encourage belonging and set up support groups for vulnerable people among FDP. For example, facilitating the work of neighbourhood associations that assist vulnerable groups.

For the adoption of similar TAISs, the Spanish ARU provides two more specific recommendations: considering the deadlines of the processes of all the beneficiaries so that they do not have to forcibly give up a TAIS, and the deprecarisation of all professional sectors.

HOW

Providing training for trainers on the specific conditions, contexts and transversal aspects related to FDP, giving them (trainers and other direct service providers) psychosocial training for a better adjustment to the beneficiary groups' realities.

In the neighbourhoods, favour the associative fabric, generating support and coexistence networks also for migrants and FDP.

Organisations and trainers must always consider the deadlines of the asylum processes of the beneficiaries and the different stages for the application of the TAIS. It is necessary to adjust the duration of the TAIS or provide alternatives.

Organisations and trainers should consider the learning processes and the specific needs of the final beneficiaries of training programs. It is necessary to dedicate more time to planning processes and outcome evaluation for the attention and inclusion programs, adapting them to FDP's needs. For this, the RAISD pilots provide methodologies such as the continuous evaluation of the programs, the participatory processes in the evaluation and the constant co-design and adaptation of the training programs.

Raise public awareness to fight for the deprecarisation of professional sectors such as cleaning and caretaking. Demanding an improvement in the rights of workers in these sectors would improve the situation of migrants and also of the non-migrant population.

Seek for FDPs' more active role in their processes and in the attention and inclusion strategies.

WHY

FDP living in Spain should be able to raise their voices and have a say in the inclusion programs and policies as they are currently quite excluded from the decision making and design of this kind of strategies, even though it is actually their fate and future what is at stake. Not considering FDP opinions, needs and active participation in all the phases of strategy design gives room to patronising practices that do not foster FDP autonomy, self-reliance and can even re-victimize FDP.

Regarding the organisations, the recruiting and composition of the final beneficiary groups is sometimes made in a hurry and without further considerations of viability. For example, migrants with children often have difficulties attending programs. In addition, as previously mentioned, depending on the length of the TAIS, FDP may be left out of the program. Depending on their situation in the process, if the deadlines of their asylum processes expire, displaced persons may be left out of the protection system and have to leave the TAIS program.

At all levels, an economic boost is necessary to promote self-employment and entrepreneurship among vulnerable groups. According to the Spanish ARU, this kind of TAIS methodology is correct, but it is important to remember that self-employment always requires a seed capital.

WHAT

Vulnerable people among FDP should be included in the design and planning process of attention and inclusion strategies. But, in addition, both the personnel of the NGOs and the forced migrants themselves must avoid and should not accept paternalistic and patronising approaches. The self-motivation and responsibility in programs and trainings ought to be fostered, FDP should provide feedback and dare to talk.

Regarding the organisations, practical aspects such as the beneficiary group homogeneity with similar aims,

needs and educational levels, or childcare services are of great importance.

The beneficiaries must receive and understand the information on the scope of the social care and inclusion programs, and to become aware of the aspects in which they should be more autonomous.

HOW

Integrating not only a sample of FDP, but actually the core of the beneficiaries in the initial design and in all phases of the inclusion strategy, including the implementation and evaluation, is a key aspect for a really tailored program that responds to FDP needs and fosters their capacitation and future options in an autonomous way.

Organisations, administrations and service providers should not offer the same solution to all FDP, but adjust each program to the requirements and profiles of the beneficiary groups, so the participants can feel more at ease within persons with similar backgrounds and educational levels, as well as motivational aspirations.

Promoting the autonomy of final beneficiaries in social care and inclusion programs. It is a process that involves the final beneficiaries and it also helps the professionals in social care and inclusion programs to avoid the already mentioned behaviours of patronising and dependency. Organisations and TAIS implementers should provide a comfortable setting and encourage migrants to give their feedback.

Integrating childcare services in the strategies and in the services offered by refugee reception centres and NGOs, even finding peer-to-peer solutions that strengthen networks and may increase the empowerment of caregivers.

Beneficiaries must be aware at all times of the deadlines of their processes. For this it is necessary that they receive adequate information, adapted to each case, and that they can have a more active role in making decisions that affect their own lives.

CESIE, ITALY

ALL YOU CAN LEARN *Inclusion a-la-carte*

The Italian TAIS counteracts the still current tendency for national educational change policymakers and planners to ignore human factors; training providers too often assume to know and understand FDPs' learning needs, thrusting learners into one-size-fits-all solutions while ignoring those individual factors and circumstances (pre-migration, in-transit, at-arrival) that strongly affect educational achievements. In Italy, this reflects in a high number of NEET (Not in Education, Employment or Training) among FDP, consistent training dropout rates and lower female participation.

The design of the selective-learning TAIS, a tool/methodology developed by CESIE in the frame of RAISD, i.e. the training opportunity "ALL you can LEARN" (AUCL), proposes a participatory practice in education, shifting from an "induced" training offer approach (i.e. a dominating and top-down way to organise education for FDPs) to a "selective" approach aimed at developing a training offer in which several optional modules are offered so that participants can choose contents that are attractive for them.

The ultimate aim was to increase learners' decision-making capacity as they are to be intended as "co-experts" of the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) based inclusion strategy, thus having the opportunity to decide and co-design their learning experience according to a set of individual variables

(interests and aspirations, level of studies and previously attended programmes, language knowledge, logistics and time availability, etc.).

Expected results of the Italian TAIS included the increased highly vulnerable and forcibly displaced female participation in Education and Training; decreased initial resistance and attendance reluctance; reduced in-training dropout rates among FDP women. In order to achieve these goals, the excessive strictness of learning paths and hours of commitment were avoided and replaced by a flexible learning environment.

The actual piloting of "ALL you can LEARN" involved Forcibly Displaced Women living and/or exposed to highly vulnerable situations and conditions, victims of human trafficking currently living in Sicily, originally from Ivory Coast, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Somalia, Comoros and Tunisia. The training experience was implemented over 16 sessions/40 hours in summer 2021, covering orientation sessions (understanding learning objectives to be achieved); actual face-to-face training sessions, based on twenty learning objectives selected by each participant; local study visits as an opportunity for debate, exchange and mutual learning and final evaluation and capitalization sessions.

Italian TAIS Testimonies <https://raisd-h2020.eu/research/aru/italy/>
<https://allyoucanlearn.cesie.org/>

Italian Good Practices <https://raisd-h2020.eu/media/d5.1-potential-aps-it.pdf>

Recommendations to improve policies and practices regarding the care of vulnerable groups

Recommendations to improve policies and practices regarding the care of vulnerable groups fitting the Italian legal and social systems, include:

- A. World level (useful for instance to UNHCR, IOM) European and international level (targeted to EU institutions and agencies)
INVEST IN SELECTIVE COURSE DESIGNS TO ENSURE AND STIMULATE MIGRANTS' LEARNING PROGRESS OVER TIME AND TO AVOID DROP-OUTS
- B. Italian Country level (national government, regional and local authorities and institutions).
BOOST LEARNERS' DECISION-MAKING CAPACITY BY ADOPTING THE NOVELTY SELECTIVE-APPROACH IN LEARNING AND TRAINING ENVIRONMENTS
- C. Host community level (ARU members/inclusion strategy implementers)
EXPLOIT THE "ALLYOU CAN TEACH" RESOURCE DATABASE FOR PROFESSIONALS IN EDUCATION IN THE FIELD OF MIGRATION
- D. Highly Vulnerable People among the Forcibly Displaced
FOSTER MIGRANTS' OWN COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT AS A BRIDGE BETWEEN NEWCOMERS AND HOSTING COMMUNITIES

Extending the innovative attention and inclusion strategy to other Vulnerable Groups and different Vulnerability Context

The AUCL selective-learning approach has been designed to respond to FDP (highly) vulnerable individuals with migratory background; for both, female and male learners' needs. When formulating the research question, both men and women, were considered and it was also analysed if and in what way men and women could be relating differently to the research problem.

RAISD provided the opportunity to pilot the approach, this time, with all highly vulnerable female participants – though its design is suitable to be adopted by a variety of other specific profiles too.

Therefore, the Italian ARU/Competence Cell will continue operating after the end of the project willing to increase the offers to select from, increase the number of users and diversify HVG profiles that can benefit from it. Given the flexible nature of the virtual organisation all thematic units are encouraged to use the tool with their own specific target groups.

The Italian TAIS results might be adopted by stakeholders (hosting communities, migrant/refugee assistant professionals and volunteers, schools, training provides, job centres, local and regional authorities) as (i) guest administrators or as (ii) adopters by implementing their own platform. with their own targets and projects.

i.As Administrator, the inclusion actor will be granted with a special access code. Profiling and mapping will be under their own consideration and responsibility. To follow the content conceptualisation process see [MENU Content](#); [Video tutorial](#) on how to navigate the AUCL MENU; [Trainees' Diary](#)

As adopters, the AUCL [Technical Requirements](#) are available to support adopters in implementing a similar platform. See also [Graphical User Interface \(GUI\) Design](#) \\ [online, as test user](#) [access user experience with group code: 6941766]

Potential adopters of the TAIS methodology, materials, products, services

Community of Users and TAIS observatory: users will belong to target groups of Vulnerable Groups (VGs), hosting communities, and migrant/refugee assistant professionals and volunteers.

- LEARN - <https://allyoucanlearn.cesie.org/learn> for FDPs and other vulnerable profiles [increased number of users and diversify HVG profiles that can benefit from it; new Learning Objectives offers to select from].
- TEACH - <https://allyoucanlearn.cesie.org/teach> (web analytics and user statistics: number of downloads, comments, new resources added) The Community of Users can register to comment and rate all current 161

educational resources. Registered users can propose new material to be uploaded to the online database.

Main outcome (intangible results) includes the novelty tool/methodology developed by CESIE, that proposes a bottom-up and participatory approach in education, shifting from INDUCED approach training offer to a SELECTIVE one, allowing adult learners to increase their decision-making capacity by having direct influence over their learning path's content and modalities according to a set of individual variables (interests and aspirations, level of studies and previously attended programmes, logistics and time availability, etc.).

Main outputs (tangible Results) to be further developed and exploited by the ARU and wider Community of Users are:

"ALL you can LEARN" Digital Learning MENU

<https://allyoucanlearn.cesie.org/learn> for FDPs and other vulnerable profiles.

The bilingual online selection tool (Italian and English) represents the digital "learning menu" that supports the testing of the TAIS SELECTIVE approach: trainees choose their learning path; digital users can cross select between different areas of knowledge/challenges to be achieved during the overall "ALL you can LEARN" training experience. Through a group code, participants access the online tool and are approached 'just' as adult learners with no indication of names or titles to their vulnerabilities.

Educational Resources for Professionals in the field of MIGRATION

<https://allyoucanlearn.cesie.org/teach/> for ARU/Observatory and Community of Users.

The RAISD Resource Database for professionals in education addressing the need for inclusive learning environments with special attention to distinctively Vulnerable Groups among the Forcibly Displaced and migrant communities in Europe. The learning materials support creative skills in education for youth, adults, vocational education and training, school communities as well as in Higher Education – supporting guidance, training and teaching material with a focus on different methodologies tailored to specific target group segments and contexts of vulnerability."

The Community of Users can register to comment and rate all current 161 educational resources. Registered users can propose new material to be uploaded to the online database.

Invest in flagship selective course designs to ensure and stimulate migrants' learning progress and to avoid drop-outs

WHY

Education and training have a vital role to play when it comes to shaping the future of Europe, at a time when it is imperative that its society and economy become more cohesive, inclusive, digital, sustainable, green and resilient, and for citizens to find personal fulfilment and wellbeing, to be prepared to adapt and perform on a changing labour market and to engage in active and responsible citizenship. The COVID-19 pandemic has put unprecedented pressure on the education and training sector and triggered a widespread shift to distance and blended teaching and learning. This shift has brought different challenges and opportunities for education and training systems and communities, unveiling the impact of the digital divide and connectivity gaps within Member States, as well as inequalities among wealth groups and urban-rural settings, while also highlighting the potential of education and training to build resilience and foster sustainable and inclusive growth.¹

WHAT

As a matter of fact, efficient planning for growing individual freedom of the students to choose courses makes planning much more complex. Due to reforms, elective courses are today an important part of the curriculum, and elective courses are a good way to make inclusive inclusion-education more attractive for the migrant learners². Selective courses are designed to promote self-determination of students and selection of further professional activities, create positive motivation for learning on the planned profile, introduce students to the leading activities for this profile, enhance learners' cognitive activities, and enhance their information and communication competence.³

By choosing elective courses students are more agitated in learning, more interested and motivated.

Research has proven that elective courses realize an important role in students' professional and personal

development by integrating knowledge of many subjects, through their participation in tailoring the curricula and enriching their professional portfolio.⁴

The elective courses allow students to shape their majors to meet their specific needs and interests.

On the other hand, education and training providers (trainers/educators/teachers/mediators) think harder over the supply of subjects and their content. At the same time, it increases educators' motivation to consider new approaches, update information, and on the whole do their best to make their subjects appealing to learners.

HOW

The selective approach allows shifting from an "induced" training offer approach (i.e. a dominating and top-down way to organise education for FDPs and leave them either accepting or rejecting the contents of education) to a "selective" approach in developing a training offer in which several optional modules are offered and participants can choose contents that are attractive for them. Highly Vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced are to be intended as "co-experts" of the strategic approach, having the opportunity to decide and co-design their personal learning experience according to a set of individual variables (interests and aspirations, level of studies and previously attended programmes, language knowledge, logistics and time availability, etc.). Based on the above, the project team recommends, to change adult education budgeting on local, national and regional levels according to these new partnerships and results of such R&I processes. Transdisciplinarity and co-creation should be set as one of the criteria, during the application process for R&I funding. Such strategies should be welcomed and supported though funding policies, since a linear approach cannot be used to find solutions to complex problems.⁵

¹ Council Resolution in education and training towards the European Education Area and beyond (2021-2030) <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/48584/st06289-re01-en21.pdf>

² S. Kristiansen, M. Sørensen, T.R. Stidsen, Elective course planning, *European Journal of Operational Research*, Volume 215, Issue 3, 2011, Pages 713-720, ISSN 0377-2217, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2011.06.039>.

³ T.B. Baynazarova, T.S. Zhumasheva, G.K. Karimbayev, E.Konyrbayeva, (2018). Elective Courses - Courses On

Selection. *SOCIAL MENTALITY AND RESEARCH THINKERS JOURNALS*, 7, p. 27-31. <https://doi.org/10.31576/smryj.34>.

⁴ Movchan, Larysa & Zarishniak, Inna. (2017). [The Role of Elective Courses in Students' Professional Development: Foreign Experience](#). *Comparative Professional Pedagogy*. 7. DOI: 10.1515/rpp-2017-0018.

⁵ Further elaboration of H2020 FoTTRIS Systems (015 – 2018) Italian [Policy recommendations for co-RRJ](#), pag. 29.

CESIE recommends to Italian Country level (government, regional, local authorities and institutions).

Boost learners' decision-making capacity by adopting the novelty selective-approach in learning and training environments

WHY

As there is still a tendency for national educational change policymakers and planners to ignore human factors, training providers too often assume to know and understand FDPs' learning needs by default, thrusting learners into one-size-fits-all solutions while ignoring those individual factors and circumstances (pre-migration, in-transit, at-arrival) that strongly affect educational achievements. The evidence for a need in 'Change Management in Education Delivery Approaches' that could focus on local/regional manifestations of global challenges and on 'local' opportunities for solving them, was suggested by the RAISD fieldwork findings under the action-research approach.⁶

The COVID-19 crisis demonstrated that education and training systems must be sufficiently flexible and resistant to interruptions in their regular cycles, and proved that EU countries have the capacity to find solutions to continue the delivery of teaching and learning processes in different ways and contexts, and to ensure that all learners, irrespective of their socioeconomic background or learning needs, continue to learn. The same applies for the framework of European cooperation, which should remain flexible enough to respond to both current and future challenges, including in the context of the European Education Area.⁷

WHAT

The design of the novelty selective-learning training opportunity 'ALL you can LEARN' (allyoucanlearn.cesie.org, 2020) also adopts the four fundamental RRI characteristics: anticipation, reflection, inclusion, responsiveness, by introducing a more bottom-up and participatory practice to education, shifting from an "induced" training offer approach (i.e. a dominating and top-down way to organise education for FDPs and leave them either accepting or rejecting the contents of education) to a "selective" approach in developing a training offer in which several optional modules are offered and participants can choose

contents that are attractive for them. The ultimate aim is to increase learners' decision-making capacity (in this specific case, Forcibly Displaced Women living and/or exposed to highly vulnerable situations and conditions) as they are to be intended as "co-experts" of the RRI based inclusion strategy, thus having the opportunity to decide and co-design their personal learning experience according to a set of individual variables (interests and aspirations, level of studies and previously attended programmes, language knowledge, logistics and time availability, etc.).

HOW

Making the practices' operational structures more flexible is necessary to meet the diverse needs of migrant learners. Such measure is crucial for those with limited time for study (such as those in full-time employment or with caring responsibilities). There, it is recommended to:

- contribute to increase beneficiaries' possibilities to choose their own professional path, owing to the fact of experiencing one (also when not corresponding perfectly with personal desires and expectations).
- contribute to improve beneficiaries' ability to orient themselves autonomously in the inclusion process and services.
- follow supporting policies for HVG through orientation activities and custody (tutorship/mentoring/role models/family integration).
- ensure implementers are ready and can deliver alternative learning and teaching methods depending on individual, interests, needs, wishes.

⁶ RAISD, "TAIS: definition and guidelines – preliminary version", 2021. <https://raisd-h2020.eu/media/raisd-d5.2-tais-definition-guidelines-preliminary.pdf>

⁷ Council Resolution on a strategic framework for European cooperation in education and training towards

the European Education Area and beyond (2021-2030) <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/48584/st06289-re01-en21.pdf>

Exploit the “ALLYOU CAN TEACH” resource database for professionals in education in the field of migration

WHY

Well-trained teachers and trainers are vital for ensuring the inclusion of immigrant and refugee pupils but they too need support in order to manage multilingual, multicultural classes, often including students with psychosocial needs. A well-designed curriculum that promotes diversity, that provides critical skills and that challenges prejudices is also vital, and can have a positive ripple effect beyond the classroom walls. Sometimes textbooks include outdated depictions of migrations and undermine efforts towards inclusion. Many curricula are also not flexible enough to work around the lifestyles of those perpetually on the move.⁸

Being a migrant is one of the most relevant predictors of school dropout, especially if associated with a low socio-economical background (Hippe and Jakubowski, 2018). Beyond that, insufficient language skills, age at migration, lack of parental support (in terms of both cultural and economic capital), and the characteristics of the host educational system are other relevant determinants of young migrants' educational disadvantage (Contini, 2013). In particular, national educational curricula are designed for native students, hence those with migrant background may have more difficulties to understand and learn contents that are far away from their knowledge heritage⁹.

WHAT

Teachers, trainers and volunteering legal guardians working with migrant and refugee students who have suffered trauma face particular hardships and need training to address the challenges and critical incidents. Teachers should be trained in the type of whole-school approach that is required for social and emotional learning interventions to be effective. Moreover, teachers' own well-being should not be neglected:

teachers need training and support to recognize and deal with their own stresses.¹⁰

Not enough training courses are offered to inclusion and social care professionals in Italy with regards to cultural competence, as well as specific needs of consequences of adverse experiences such as trauma, violence, and trafficking. Therefore, there is a need to support the work of social workers, teachers and trainers who sustain FDP and migrants in general in the inclusion process within the new local and national context to minimize learning and teaching disparities through the up-skilling of teachers on issues related to teaching learning with migrant backgrounds, diversity management in the educational settings and promoting inclusion.

HOW

The [RAISD \ ALL YOU CAN LEARN Resource Database for professionals in education](https://allyoucanlearn.cesie.org/teach/) was designed during the first COVID-19 lockdown period in 2020, when there was a forced increase of distance learning methods and approaches in education and training, that found professionals in need for guidance, training and teaching material with a focus on different methodologies tailored to specific target group segments and contexts of vulnerability. Here the need to provide for a Resource Database to address the need for inclusive learning environments with special attention to distinctively Vulnerable Groups among the Forcibly Displaced and migrant communities in Europe. The learning materials aim to support creative skills in education for youth, adults, vocational education and training, school communities as well as in Higher Education. The Community of Users can register to comment and rate all current 161 educational resources. Registered users can propose new material to be uploaded to the online database. <https://allyoucanlearn.cesie.org/teach/>.

⁸ UNESCO. 2018. Global Education Monitoring Report 2019: Migration, Displacement and Education – Building Bridges, not Walls. Paris, UNESCO

⁹ Lamonica, V., Ragazzi, E. & Sella, L. Including adolescent migrants in school through VET approach: evidence from a pilot action in Italy. *Empirical Res Voc Ed Train* 12, 6 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40461-020-00092-x>

¹⁰ Terres des Homes, FARO Project, 2017. Psychosocial Handbook for Social Workers in charge of receiving unaccompanied foreign minors. Best practices on how to give mental health and psychosocial support to child refugees and migrants [url](https://www.terresdeshomes.org/).

Foster Migrants' own community engagement as a bridge between newcomers and hosting communities

WHY

Especially for non-EU citizens, immigration to a new country means a new set of challenges that are usually derived from: a) lack of information about how the organizational systems of the country they have entered (economic, social, health, educational, work, etc.) function, b) lack of language skills to work with usual information channels. This problem is specifically difficult to tackle for the people who speak fluently neither in the host country language, nor in English. For these persons usually the only information channel available is their own ethnic diaspora, making it quite difficult to tackle issues of daily life without the help of their compatriots. Mentoring and training migrants require the establishment of a relationship based on esteem and trust. However, the high degree of isolation and the vulnerability of migrants lead to develop dynamics of dependence in the hope that the mentor/trainer can intercede for the resolution of health, work, economic and legal issues. It could be useful to create a buddy or mentoring system with long-term residents or other professionals.¹¹

WHAT

Unlike their parents, the 1.5 (people who immigrate to the new country before or during their early teens) and the second-generation migrants are usually already fully integrated into the majority society. They are fluent in the host country language, and they often spend most of their free time in the local cultural environment (schools, clubs, sport teams, etc.), where they acquire local habits and behaviour. On the one hand, this fact may cause conflicts between generations (esp. in the cases of communities culturally and religiously different from the majority society); on the other hand, it represents an opportunity. As these individuals have an inimitable set of competencies arising from their migrant background, they may work as bridge builders with majority society, a

task which cannot be done satisfactorily by the first-generation immigrants due to their linguistic and cultural barriers. Moreover, migrants from ethnic minorities often do not have any role models in future-oriented fields throughout their job careers or health conditions, neither within their families nor in their social contexts. Therefore, it is considered crucial to offer support figures from their own ethnic communities who accompany them on their way to a successful autonomy. The matching process enables shared language and culture and similar experiences to strengthen the mentoring relationships and the mentor's ability to empathize and understand the experiences of the young mentee, and the mentee to have someone to identify with.

HOW

1.5/2nd generation migrants will be able to offer adequate consultation to refugees, asylum seekers and migrants facilitating not only the communication and exchange between them and the hosting authorities and societies, but also their social integration, well-being and guidance within the EU environment. Well-supported migrants settle and feel included faster, help create a strong and vibrant community, boost regional growth and wellbeing, find it easier to participate in and contribute to economic, civic and social life. Therefore, it is recommended to equip 1.5 and second-generation migrants with skills, competences, and knowledge necessary to act as intercultural workers within their communities by building on their unique cultural assets. As such, they will be able to serve as a link between the migrant community and local people, thereby contributing to better integration of the newcomers, and the first-generation migrants. The opportunity to educate this target group for intercultural work aptly responds to increasing demand for qualified intercultural workers who would help migrant communities in their local context.

¹¹ RAISD, "Catalogue of Attention and Inclusion Practices for FDP in the EU influence area – Italy", 2020.
<https://raisd-h2020.eu/media/d5.1-potential-gps-it.pdf>

The logo of the University of Helsinki, Finland, is a large, abstract geometric shape composed of many overlapping triangles in various colors including purple, red, orange, yellow, green, and blue. The text "University of Helsinki, FINLAND" is centered within this shape in a white, sans-serif font.

University of Helsinki, FINLAND

I. Multilingual online forum

Young asylum-seeking men are rarely considered as suffering from vulnerabilities even though they constitute a highly discriminated group in Finland and few services are targeted for them. Many men lack the opportunities to use and learn everyday language with Finnish-speaking peers while most of the contacts they have with Finnish-speakers are reception center professionals and elderly women since they tend to volunteer through NGOs. Particularly in smaller towns and rural areas there are few possibilities in contacting Finnish-speaking peers. Moreover, according to several asylum seeker interviews, the language tuition within the reception centers is not enough, is restricted to classrooms and is too repetitive due to constantly changing teachers and learners and the huge diversity of educational backgrounds different asylum seekers have.

To respond to the above problems, a voluntary group of young asylum-seeking men were invited to join, together with Finnish-speaking voluntary young men,

in an online thread to discuss the experiences of asylum seekers and everyday life in the Finnish society. The aim was to promote the learning of both asylum seekers and voluntaries. The former group will learn the language, Finnish culture from the perspective of ordinary men and may find more information about various possibilities Finland. As for the latter group, voluntary men are able to have a first-hand knowledge about the lives of asylum seekers in Finland and about their home countries. Further, both groups will develop their skills in online communications.

The online discussions were moderated and, when necessary, translated from languages used by asylum seekers into Finnish. At least one asylum seeking peer moderator was recruited during the second and third piloting rounds to instigate discussions and, when necessary, to help in translating the messages. Each forum lasted approximately five weeks.

2. Development of child-care services in Finnish reception centres

TAIS aimed to develop child-care services in reception centres in Finland. Currently, asylum-seeking families do not have the right to early childhood education in municipal day-care centres before the pre-school at the age of six. Moreover, reception centres are not obligated to provide child-care and the level of child-care services provided varies significantly between different reception centres. Lack of child-care services has repercussions on both parental and child wellbeing: parents are not able to focus on their own wellbeing and settlement and their children are segregated from Finnish speaking peers and miss structured activities supporting their learning and development.

To promote the wellbeing of asylum-seeking families with small children, child-care activities were developed together with the Finnish Red Cross (FRC) reception centres. The general state of child-care services in FRC reception centres was surveyed and

two reception centres providing comparatively wide-ranging child-care services were involved to develop their activities further. Child-care activities of the two centres were observed and parents and professionals involved were interviewed. The knowledge acquired was used to qualitatively improve the content of the child-care activities. Moreover, a trial of more intensive child-care activities was carried out in one reception centre. The service hours were increased for a period of nine weeks and families were provided lifts to ease the use of the services.

As a result, a model for child-care services for reception centres will be established to be used for all reception centres throughout Finland. Moreover, the knowledge collected in the TAIS will be used to argue the importance of asylum-seeking children's access to municipal early childhood education and care services.

Finnish TAIS Testimonies <https://raisd-h2020.eu/research/aru/finland/>

Finnish Good Practices <https://raisd-h2020.eu/media/d5.1-potential-gps-fi.pdf>

Recommendations to improve policies and practices regarding the care of vulnerable groups

On an international level, we recommend reconsidering the notion of vulnerability used in legislative texts and particularly in political discourse. Instead of merely inherent feature of certain individuals or groups, vulnerability should be also seen as a contextual and situational phenomenon. This type of shift would allow seeing vulnerabilities also in (young) men and avoid victimizing child and female refugees. Moreover, seeing vulnerability as contextual and situational would help to avoid rough and fixed hierarchies between different FDP and enable critically examining the categories of deserving (vulnerable) and undeserving (not vulnerable) refugees. On a national level, we recommend some changes in the Finnish reception system. The main issue is to make certain adjustments to allow asylum seekers to accommodate themselves in local communities, in education and labour market. Currently, the reception system tends to confine asylum seekers instead of promoting their inclusion to local communities and institutions. To reach this aim, instead of stressing the control functions, reception centre service provision would benefit, for instance, from the following practices: rearranging the interior design of centres to fit the needs of asylum seekers, reducing the demarcation between professionals and asylum seekers with spatial practices, revising the service provision to better promote education and employment opportunities and invest more in multilingual communication and hire lingually competent personnel.

Furthermore, we also recommend national authorities to be more sensitive toward certain sub-groups of previously unrecognised asylum seekers: young men and particularly single parents with small children. For instance, NGOs working in the field of refugee and asylum seeker reception need to focus more on recruiting male voluntary workers. Since their recruitment will probably be a challenging task in the future as well, online methods need to be developed to be able to share the input of the male voluntaries in more peripheral localities as well. As for asylum-seeking families with small children, childcare need to be provided to enhance both parents' and children's inclusion. As the responsibility of care of children in families often relies on mothers, providing childcare services could be a step to decrease the victim position of asylum-seeking women by providing them a possibility to study, work or take care of themselves, and in that way increase their capabilities and capacities.

Extending the innovative attention and inclusion strategy to other Vulnerable Groups and different Vulnerability Context

The TAIS 1 was designed in a very specific context and for a specific group, young asylum-seeking men living in peripheral areas of Finland. It is likely that the need for this type of activity is more modest in other partners in RAISD consortium. However, the situation with young male asylum seekers is quite similar throughout Northern and to some extent Central Europe (e.g., Sweden, Norway, Germany and Austria). Asylum seekers are mostly young single men lacking connections to local men and paths of inclusion while local NGOs have few answers to such problems. Consequently, this TAIS could be scaled at least to other Nordic contexts, not necessarily to Middle East or Southern Europe. The planning and implementation of the TAIS requires only some extra resources. The idea is that voluntaries are the ones making the TAIS possible in an already existing and free-of-charge platform (Discord). However, there is a need for at least one expert. His/her task is to train the volunteers, invite people to join the forum, follow and moderate the online discussions and be prepared to intervene when help is needed.

The childcare services developed and evaluated in the TAIS 2 are designed for asylum-seeking children in the context of Finnish reception centres. However, the basic model of childcare services can be adjusted in other contexts as well and can be extended to other (vulnerable) groups of children. However, there are differences between countries in asylum seekers access to public childcare or pre-school education. These differences need to be taken into account when thinking about scaling TAIS 2 in other contexts. In any case, the used

methodology of mediating between service providers (reception centre workers) and service users (asylum-seeking parents) to develop existing services can be applied in other vulnerable groups and contexts as well. Providing child-care through reception centres requires resources. Depending on the amount of below school-age children, there is a need for at least two part-time professionals, distinct and safe rooms for organising the activities and various materials (toys, tables, chairs, kitchen etc.).

Potential adopters of the TAIS methodology, materials, products, services

Regarding the TAIS 1, NGOs in Northern Europe and particularly the Nordic region. Unfortunately, it is highly unlikely that the Finnish Immigration Service would adopt methods stressing the inclusion of asylum seekers. Their main focus is to fulfil the legal requirements which do not encourage investing in methods helping asylum seekers to build connections outside reception centres. Therefore, in the Finnish context, the Finnish Red Cross or some other more humanitarian organisation would be more likely to adopt the method.

The model of childcare services created in the TAIS 2 could help the coordinating authorities (The Finnish Immigration Service and The Finnish Red Cross) and other local actors (reception centres) to implement good quality child-care services. The modelling can be utilized to improve existing childcare services or to establish new services in reception centres in Finland. With readjustment, the model can be used in other countries as well. Moreover, the TAIS results that show the benefits of childcare services for asylum-seeking children could encourage Finnish local authorities to allow asylum-seeking children to enrol in municipal early childcare education.

Revise the notion of vulnerability by detaching it from fixed ideas about certain individuals and groups

WHY

Global actors, such as UNHCR, have a key role in setting the dominant discourse on the notion of vulnerability. Very often, the dominant idea on vulnerability relies on essentialist notions of certain groups of people. Constantly resorting to the 'women-and-children' discourse while defining the notion of vulnerability is harmful to both women and children and to men as well. First, this dominant discourse reinforces the distinction between deserving and undeserving FDPs thus strengthening racism toward refugee and asylum-seeking men throughout the world. Second, the discourse victimizes women and children and denies their agency while men are seen as potential perpetrators.

WHAT

The notion of vulnerability needs to be seen as contextual and situational. The same person can be resilient in one context/situation and vulnerable in some

other. Also, young men can be vulnerable in certain conditions and situations. Further, (young) men themselves would probably benefit from being able to present them as vulnerable instead of performing traditional masculinities. Instead of only listing vulnerable groups, global organisations need to approach vulnerability in more sensitive manners and see the differences between various regions and situations.

HOW

It is a matter of discourse and cultural definitions and starts from various programs and documents of different organisations. There are plenty of evidence on how men are lacking recognition as a vulnerable group: few supporting measures are designed for them and existing measures are mostly relying on control. Moreover, victimized women are often targeted by certain measures instead of seeing them as capable actors who could design their own programs.

HU recommends to Finnish Country level (government, regional, local authorities and institutions).

Asylum-seeking families should have the right in early childhood education and care services in municipal day-care centres

WHY

Currently, most asylum-seeking children have no right to early childhood education and care in municipal day-care centres. A few exceptions exist: Firstly, in very few cities, all children (including asylum-seekers and undocumented), or all children over 5 years are entitled to municipal day-care. Secondly, asylum-seeking children can get the access to municipal day-care (paid by the state) in the case of severe health or social issues in the family, estimated by social service or health care professionals.

Consequently, most asylum-seeking children enter the Finnish education system in pre-school at the age of six. Moreover, reception centres are not obligated to provide child-care services and the level of provided activities varies between the centres.

For many families, this type of context tends to cause problems and aggravate already existing ones in a very stressful situation. Parents have difficulties in using the services they are entitled to and their abilities to work or educate themselves and rest are highly limited. Children miss structured activities, professional support in their development and learning, and are separated from their Finnish-speaking peers. Therefore, asylum-seeking children's access to early childhood education and care services is important for both children and their parents to support their wellbeing and inclusion.

Moreover, this would be beneficial for the society as well. Preventing problems of children by providing early childhood education may be more economical than remedial support that may be needed if a child enters the school system at age of six only after being separated from the system and Finnish peers for years. Furthermore, daily day-care would not promote only integration of children but also their parents (mothers), responding to the worried public discussion about immigrant women's integration.

WHAT

Asylum-seeking families' right to early childhood education and care services should be granted in the national legislation. As long as this is not possible, municipalities should ensure asylum-seeking children's access to municipal day-care services.

HOW

Some municipalities in Finland have decided to provide early childhood education and care services for all children including asylum-seeking and undocumented children.

In some municipalities, all 5-year old children are provided free access. In some municipalities, the price of day-care of asylum-seeking children (provided by the municipality in day-care centres and paid by the Finnish Immigration Service) are negotiated to be lower than the actual costs.

After the covid-19 pandemic, a more coherent and systematic body of online methods need to be developed in the work with FDP

WHY

In the Finnish reception system, during the times of social distancing, only few online methods were developed to support asylum seekers in their daily lives and integration efforts. In the Finnish context in which reception centres are located in quite peripheral areas, online methods and support might have a big relevance. Voluntary workers, educators, legal support and various face-to-face services are rarely available in the living spheres of many asylum seekers. Obviously, a key issue would be to relocate the reception centres into more central areas but this type of development is unlikely to happen in the near future.

WHAT

Within the reception system, there needs to be systematic consideration about the potential benefits of online methods in order to support and engage asylum seekers. While designing services, asylum seekers need to be included in the work. Since asylum seekers as

required to do either study or work activities in order to earn their reception benefit, these activities could also include their engagement into service designing work. In average, asylum seekers are most keen in participating in piloting activities during the first months of their stay. In case of protracted asylum processes the motivation understandably tends to decrease.

HOW

Certain organisations, such as Immigration Service and Red Cross need to appoint a person responsible of developing online methods. This would be the start. It seems as if nobody oversees this type of developmental work. In addition to providing social support for asylum seekers, online channels could be developed to share multilingual information among asylum seekers. Currently, information is shared in a traditional form in bulletin boards in the offices of reception centres. Those asylum seekers who have few reasons to visit the offices, might miss some of the relevant information.

The Finnish reception services need to promote the agency of asylum seekers more systematically

WHY

According to our research results, Finnish reception services tend to isolate asylum seekers from the surrounding society and communities. The main function of the system is to confine and control asylum seekers while their applications are processed. Since the processes can take several years, it would be wise to invest more effort on helping asylum seekers to build connections to surrounding communities and institutions.

WHAT

In relation to asylum seeking young adults, there needs to be more services focusing on labour market and education counselling. Currently, these types of services are practically absent in reception centres. A further

practice to promote asylum seekers' agency would be to recruit lingually competent employees to work as counsellors. This would enhance the flow of correct information and the autonomy of asylum seekers right after entering the country.

HOW

Obviously, a change in the service system would require legislative changes to make inclusive work more legitimate. In addition to structural changes, there is a need to do bold experiments even if they would fail. Currently, individual reception centres are quite free to test various practices to develop their service provision. In many cases, the problem is a lack of coordination and inability to scale various good practises.

Trajectory monitoring toolbox for social workers working with refugees

In Hungary, the objective of the TAIS is to enhance refugees' embeddedness in social structures. Social workers and service providers analysed individual cases in order to build a "Trajectory monitoring toolbox" of helpful and tailored interventions for vulnerable refugees.

The toolbox was built around evidence-based "vulnerability profiles" and the description of the trajectories that these typical cases should follow in the institutional field to prevent the accumulation of vulnerabilities and reduce the isolation of vulnerable individuals. Social workers and service providers in Hungary should be informed about who, where, and how to apply helpful and tailored interventions for vulnerable refugees.

The toolbox has the primary objective to recognise and assess a context of vulnerability. Also, institutions and organisations can improve their internal workflow, as well as for inter-institutional cooperation, to make trajectories less demanding and vulnerability reduction more effective.

The toolbox contains two major elements:

1. Handbook. We transferred the research results of vulnerability contexts into training exercises, offering a practical task collection that processes the vulnerability of refugees living in Hungary along with current, real-life situations.
2. Self-reflection tool. To address the lack of self-reflection in the daily practices of service providers, we built a new pilot program involving the social workers, and ARUs to develop a methodological system for self-reflection. From this, a tool evolved based on the results of the project.

The development of the TAIS was a research-based interdependent process in which the core team adjusted the initial hypotheses to address and respond to the aspects that evolved over the piloting phase. It was a dynamic method that required the constant involvement and feedback of the beneficiaries and ARU members.

Hungarian TAIS Testimonies <https://raisd-h2020.eu/research/aru/hungary/>

Hungarian Good Practices <https://raisd-h2020.eu/media/d5.1-potential-gps-hu.pdf>

Recommendations to improve policies and practices regarding the care of vulnerable groups

In Hungary, social protection of vulnerable groups in general is a neglected and underfunded policy area. It would therefore be important to place this topic higher on the policy agenda and to provide more funds for programmes that aim at reducing vulnerabilities.

Within the topic of social protection in general, the social protection of refugees is a particularly neglected topic. Since the government phased out the integration contract in 2016 and cut the funding of NGOs working in the field in 2018 (by making the EU's AMIF fund unavailable for them), integration policy is practically non-existent in Hungary. These measures are clearly related to the government's anti-refugee rhetoric and policies. Bringing the integration contract back, providing access for NGOs to AMIF funds, and stopping harsh anti-refugee propaganda would be necessary to build up a stable network of institutions and stakeholders that take care of vulnerable refugees.

The recent refugee wave, caused by Russia's devastating attack on Ukraine, has had a severe impact on the public and NGO sector dealing with migration and asylum issues in Hungary. At the time of the finalization of this report (11 March 2022) it is not yet clear, to what extent state-level policies of refugee integration will be changed in response to the crisis. In all cases, evidence stemming from the RAISD project points at the crucial importance of the meso level institutions (organizations working with vulnerable individuals) in order to provide professional and tailored assistance.

Extending the innovative attention and inclusion strategy to other Vulnerable Groups and different Vulnerability Context

Based on our TAIS, it can be stated that many of the vulnerabilities identified are not specific to Beneficiaries of International Protection (BIPs) only. Other foreigners with residence permit linked to employment, education or family reunification can also experience several contextual factors of vulnerability in Hungary.

The key results of our TAIS are the handbook for social workers and the template for self-reflection in social work. Both of them can be easily adapted to the characteristics of different types of foreigners.

Traditionally, beneficiaries of international protection in Hungary have arrived from the Middle East and North Africa, therefore the handbook for social workers lists examples of vulnerabilities based on profiles of individuals arriving from these regions. Recently, the arrival of forcibly displaced people from Ukraine makes it important to transfer the knowledge accumulated by social workers about refugees from the Middle East and North Africa, to organizations that are newcomers in the field and that try to address the needs of Ukrainians in Hungary. This transfer of knowledge must go hand in hand with the adaptation of the culture-specific topics to this new target group.

Another extension of the target group can also be carried out, especially if we take into account that many times the people who help refugees are not professional social workers but volunteers. The handbook and the self-reflection template can be useful tools for training volunteers – e.g. high school students who participate in a volunteering programme – so they become aware of the special needs of refugees and other foreigners.

Potential adopters of the TAIS methodology, materials, products, services

Results of our TAIS could be useful for all services providers who work with vulnerable groups.

The handbook is structured in a way that the content can be adapted to the special needs of other, non-migrant groups as well (e.g. the Roma), although it needs a careful tailoring of the profiles and the training exercises.

The self-reflection template can also be tailored and adapted to the internal structure and workflow of other service provider institutions. It has been tested in the individual social work carried out by social workers at Menedék, and it reflects this organization's way of handling complex cases. Other organizations might have different ways of operating, but the template might be adapted to their needs.

Concrete examples for possible adopters are Hungarian NGOs working with foreigners (e.g. Kalunba, Next Step, Artemisszió etc) most of which are already participating in the work of the ARUs. Organizations previously not involved in migration and asylum related topics that have recently started to help forcibly displaced people arriving from Ukraine can also benefit from the TAIS results.

Also, family support centres run by the local governments can incorporate the TAIS results to their work. However, self-reflection in social work is a complex issue, and sharing the template itself is not enough: trainings and workshops should be organized in order to provide a better understanding of concepts like interculturality to future users.

Provide access for NGOs to AMIF funds in the EU's next MFF should be ensured

WHY

The Hungarian government cut the funding of NGOs working in the field in 2018 (by making the EU's AMIF fund unavailable for them, and not providing any other sources). Because of this, integration policy is practically non-existent in Hungary.

A national level Integration Strategy for refugees and other foreigners is also lacking.

The war in Ukraine led to an unprecedented refugee wave arriving to EU's eastern member states, where refugee inclusion strategies had been scarce and not very differentiated.

WHAT

Providing access for NGOs to AMIF funds in the EU's next MFF should be ensured.

A national level Integration Strategy for foreigners should be adopted.

A comprehensive plan for attending and integrating vulnerable individuals arriving from Ukraine should be designed and implemented.

HOW

Ongoing negotiations about the MFF 2021-2027 budget should handle it as a priority.

The European Commission should provide access for Hungarian government institutions to AMIF funds only if the country adopts an Integration Strategy for foreigners.

All EU-led efforts to attend forcibly displaced persons from Ukraine must have a clear focus on different vulnerabilities and on evidence-based solutions to address these vulnerabilities.

Menedék recommends to Hungarian Country level (government, regional, local authorities and institutions).

Institutions that provide services to refugees should actively focus on self-reflection and interculturality

WHY

The war in Ukraine led to an unprecedented refugee wave arriving to Hungary, where refugee inclusion strategies had been scarce and not very differentiated.

It has been identified as a major challenge that social work with refugees / foreigners is absent from the curriculum of teaching professional social workers. Because of this, people who work with refugees have no previous knowledge about their needs.

The institutions that provide services to refugees do not actively focus on self-reflection and interculturality. Because of this, it might happen that the services they provide and the solutions they propose are not what the refugee actually needs.

Specific institutions (e.g. schools, family support centres, homeless shelters, border police etc) do not receive specific instructions from the central governance bodies about needs and rights of BIPs with whom they might get into contact.

5. A cross-cutting issue is language learning. Those who have at least a basic understanding of Hungarian can overcome their difficulties with much more success.

WHAT

An overarching national coordination mechanism should link government institutions and NGOs helping forcibly displaced individuals from Ukraine and from elsewhere.

Refugee-specific knowledge should be taught to students who want to become social workers.

Self-reflection should be an integral part of social work with refugees and specific institutions (e.g. schools, family support centres, homeless shelters, border police etc) should receive specific instructions from the central governance bodies about needs and rights of BIPs.

Free Hungarian courses should be provided to all BIPs.

HOW

A coordination mechanism already existing on the grassroots level should be formalized and given government funding in order to effectively cope with the needs of vulnerable individuals arriving from Ukraine.

A refugee-specific module should be added to the curriculum of students who want to become social workers.

The institutions that provide services to refugees should organize regular workshops or trainings to their social workers with a focus on self-reflection and interculturality.

Specific institutions (e.g. schools, family support centres, homeless shelters, border police etc) should be provided with regular workshops or trainings about the needs and rights of BIPs.

NGOs, language schools etc. should receive public funding in order to provide Hungarian courses to BIPs.

Members of the foreigner community, the host community, NGOs etc. should maintain a regular exchange of information about rights and needs

WHY

It has been shown by the TAIS that successful integration of foreigners in Hungary is usually based on the existence of a supporting network. Members of the network can be other foreigners, members of the host society, NGOs, churches, co-workers etc.

Sometimes this network builds up organically around a foreigner, but sometimes it does not. Building up such a protective network can be facilitated and promoted.

In times of crisis, social solidarity might flare up, but it is important to keep it on a high level until all needs are addressed. Institutionalization of networks and tailoring of services are necessary in order to maintain an issue high on the agenda.

WHAT

Members of the foreigner community, the host community, NGOs etc. should maintain a regular exchange of information about rights and needs of BIPs, and help individuals in need.

Those willing to help refugees should be connected to existing networks of volunteers, NGOs, official institutions, and accumulate the necessary knowledge in order to effectively help vulnerable individuals.

HOW

Regular meetings, group activities, linkages between professional NGOs and volunteering individuals or informal groups should be scheduled and administered. Knowledge-sharing platforms should be created, maintained and regularly updated.

Set a stronger network of official institutions and NGOs revolving around specific needs of vulnerable groups

WHY

Highly vulnerable individuals among the forcibly displaced often find themselves in an institutional setting in which none of the official institutions or relief organizations are able to fully address their complex needs. This might lead to a sense of abandonment and despair.

Understanding that solutions are complex and that there are various stakeholders who might be parts of the solution, but none of them is able to resolve the totality of the problem, is crucial for vulnerable individuals in order to develop a well-functioning relation towards the relevant stakeholders.

WHAT

A stronger network of official institutions and NGOs revolving around specific needs of vulnerable groups should be built upon the existing networks that usually do not include many vulnerable individuals. Ensuring participation and channelling their voice into these networks is necessary.

HOW

Based on the experience of the TAIS, direct involvement of vulnerable refugees in stakeholder discussions is difficult, as most of them do not speak Hungarian.

A dual model could work better, in which a primary group of Hungarian speaker social workers, officials, NGO workers etc. work together on a regular basis, and they reach out to refugee communities or individuals based on the knowledge they acquire in this primary group, with the help of translators or intercultural mediators.

Anadolou Uiversity, TURKEY

Accessing and Participating in Basic Daily life Practices Through Monitoring

The Turkish TAIS aims to develop capacity to help the service providers to monitor service quality on the specific needs and challenges (especially regarding the challenges being experienced while accessing the daily life practices) of forcibly displaced women and girls.

This TAIS is implemented in 2 main stages: assessment of service providers working with vulnerable groups on behalf of the government and assessment of capacity of service providers to monitor service quality on the specific needs and challenges. Firstly, service providers should have knowledge about the need-based approach, rights-based approach and advocacy issues when working with vulnerable groups. In this context, inclusion, diversity and monitoring trainings will be provided to service providers. The aim of the trainings is to provide basic information to service providers on inclusion, diversity and monitoring issues and to measure their knowledge, skills and attitudes in these matters. Pre-test and post-test method will be used to measure the impact of each training.

The second stage is the assessment of capacity of service providers to monitor service quality on the specific needs and challenges. In this regard, three

types of data collecting method will be used during monitoring:

Discovery/open ended questions: As discussed during our ARU meetings, most refugees are not aware of their rights. With open-ended questions, it is aimed to find out what refugees are aware of and what they need in terms of their rights.

Structured questions: At this stage, there will be structured questions about their access to health services and rights mechanisms etc.

Environmental scanning: Considering cultural differences, especially women and girls may have problems expressing themselves on personal issues. Especially, it can be difficult for refugee women to communicate on issues such as violence, sexual violence and abuse. At this stage, the environment in which refugees live, their relations with their environment, and the non-verbal communication they use can provide data about them. For this reason, the people who will perform the monitoring must have the ability to observe and make sense of the environment in which refugees live. Environmental scanning training will be provided during the monitoring training, and the data obtained through environmental scanning will be evaluated in the output of the monitoring phase.

Turkish TAIS Testimonies <https://raisd-h2020.eu/research/aru/turkey/>

Turkish Good Practices <https://raisd-h2020.eu/media/d5.1-potential-gps-tr.pdf>

Recommendations to improve policies and practices regarding the care of vulnerable groups

The preparation and implementation phases of our TAIS shows that depending on the VC of the country, collecting data regarding certain social groups which can be considered as “highly vulnerable” might require special attention and appropriate data collecting tools. In the case of Turkey, gender can be considered a significantly determinant factor which can affect the experiences of individuals. Therefore, addressing the issues brought about by the microlevel characteristics such as sex, gender or sexual orientation totally depends on the collection of detailed data and adapting social services accordingly. This situation brings forward the importance of developing appropriate monitoring methods, tools and improving the knowledge, skills and attitudes of human resources who are responsible for the execution of the monitoring.

Turkish TAIS mainly aims to present a model that can be adapted by local policy makers, local authorities and service providers. It is of high importance to pay attention to the fact that execution of monitoring takes place within the vulnerability context of a certain territory. Because VC can change over time and across territories, monitoring should be repeated and the data should be updated through time in order to provide effective and tailored services. Moreover, institutions should provide trainings for their social workers to improve their knowledge, skills and attitudes by adopting an inclusive and diverse approach.

Extending the innovative attention and inclusion strategy to other Vulnerable Groups and different Vulnerability Context

Because in Turkey women and girls are highly vulnerable groups, based on our TAIS, maternal women and girls are one of the specific target groups (for more information please see Annex 3). But as mentioned above, gender is a critical factor in daily life practices. Especially in less developed countries, some groups are also highly vulnerable such as LGBTQI+ community. With some exceptions, they do not have legal rights and in some countries, they even face death penalties. So, it is vital to provide a monitoring tool for local service providers to develop a better understanding regarding LGBTQI+ rights. Besides, vulnerability could vary in different regions and it brings different vulnerability contexts. Turkish TAIS could be used as a model to ensure the collaboration between the research community and local institutions to collect specific and up to date data regarding the highly vulnerable and neglected social groups.

Potential adopters of the TAIS methodology, materials, products, services

As a result of our TAIS, training materials for local government social workers were obtained. In addition, data was gathered from the diversity and cultural diversity pre-tests in the TAIS pilot phase and the cultural diversity post-tests conducted after the TAIS main trainings. This shows that at the end of the trainings, the trainees are informed about concepts such as diversity, cultural diversity, vulnerability, and forcibly displaced people. In addition, social services workers stated that these trainings were not carried out before and they demanded that the training be made continuous in the following processes. This information was found useful by the local government and they expressed their willingness to use the documents and services obtained at the end of the training. The training was given only to Eskişehir Metropolitan Municipality social services employees, but Eskişehir Tepebaşı and Odunpazarı Municipalities also reached us and said that they were aware of this project through the employees who attended the trainings. They stated that they want to apply the training we have implemented within the scope of our TAIS, to their own municipal employees as well.

Anadolu University RAISD group received an invitation from Eskişehir Bar Association to promote the project in a seminar. At the end of the seminar, the institution stated that they would like to implement such a training for its employees who work with forcibly displaced people in its sector. In addition, the institution stated that it established its own unit on equality and non-discrimination, inspired by the RAISD project. Among the RAISD Anadolu University ARU members, there were academicians from Eskişehir Anadolu University and Osmangazi University. Our ARU members were included in the communication groups established during the TAIS trainings, and the training outputs and the feedback of the participants were shared with them. Universities also stated that they want to enter into a formation in line with these outputs.

Create training programmes for social workers to develop capacity to monitor service quality on the specific needs and challenges

WHY

It is of great importance that local government personnel working with forcibly displaced groups must have knowledge of intercultural communication, diversity and especially gender issues. Local governments are working with international organisations to provide refugee women and children with access to food, shelter, clean water, education and work. International organisations such as the International Organisation for Migration (IOM), the United Nations Refugee Agency (UNHCR) and the European Union (EU) work in cooperation with local governments for the integration of forcibly displaced people into the host community. These organisations generally help country governments in matters such as economic funds for basic needs, organisational and managerial knowledge transfer. When we look at the practices carried out on an international basis with regard to refugee women and girls, it can be seen that institutions such as IOM and UNHCR carry out specific practices in the regions. For example, UNHCR is running a special project on women's vulnerability during the Covid-19 period¹². In addition, IOM within the scope of the Women in Displacement project, carried out a project dealing with gender-based problems such as discrimination, harassment, rape¹³. It is obvious that international institutions need to work together with local governments to address the problems of refugee women and girls. In addition to the personnel working directly with the vulnerable and forcibly displaced refugee women and girls in the local government, gaining gender sensitivity both in their own country and at the international level will have a reformative and developing effect in their communication with refugee women and girls. In this sense, sustainable and monitorable training plans for local government employees, as presented in our TAIS, by international institutions and local governments around the world will be beneficial.

WHAT

At the international level, an educational practice guide should be created for local governments for executing the training. This guide should be created in cooperation with all countries hosting refugees.

Vulnerability context should be taken into account when developing the guideline. Also, a "hub" should be established to enable experience sharing between local governments from participant countries. And after the establishment of the hub, municipalities should be informed and possible partner organisations should be contacted through the hub. A supervisory board should be established with a representative from all participants for the execution and operation. Hereunder a training programme about how to work with refugees within the context of need-based and right-based approach can be developed. Also, a monitoring guide can be developed by international institutions for use by all countries. In addition to this on an international scale, how countries implement inclusion and follow-up training in their local governments should be traceable by institutions.

HOW

In this context, a gender training programme can be prepared for staff working with forcibly displaced women and girls, at the international level. In this programme, a guide can be presented on how to offer solutions by local governments in the context of gender sensitivities, use of language regarding gender, communication with women and girls who have been sexually abused or harassed, sex trafficking. Furthermore, meetings can be held annually by international institutions on the current problems and solutions of women and girls who have been forcibly displaced. Host communities, local authorities and forcibly displaced women themselves should attend these meetings. Current problems can be determined at the meetings and the implementation program can be revised and improved every year.

As mentioned before, practices related to forcibly displaced women and girls at the international level are carried out on a project basis. These projects can be carried out in cooperation with local governments. Regarding the hub, a large fund should be created to keep the hub alive with crowdfunding from municipalities, NGOs and other institutions. Thus, the hub will become a common platform for all.

¹² UNHCR, 2021 t.ly/MIca

¹³ <https://womenindisplacement.org>

AU recommends to Turkish Country level (government, regional, local authorities and institutions).

Establish an observatory by national government, local government and universities cooperation

WHY

The national government and local authorities working with forcibly displaced people in Turkey, are working to meet the basic needs of refugees such as access to food, shelter, clean water, education and work. However, while carrying out these works, it does not provide training for its personnel in the integration of forcibly displaced people into the host community. As a host country, since Turkey has been dealing with gender discrimination, women and girls face problems such as discrimination, harassment, rape, mobbing, and access to education, both within the family and in social life and professional life. In a host society with gender vulnerabilities, there is an extra vulnerability for refugee women and girls. Universities carry out projects on gender and forcibly displaced people, sometimes alone and sometimes in collaboration with local or national institutions. However, a training program for social workers working with forcibly displaced women and girls and the establishment of an observatory to monitor this process are of great importance. When the intellectual knowledge of the university and the field experience of the administration come together, a permanent observatory will enable social workers to develop on gender issues. At the same time, it will enable the supervision of services carried out by observing the rights of refugee women and girls who have been forcibly displaced.

WHAT

New arrangements can be made for local government employees who come into contact with forcibly displaced women and girls at any level in Turkey to receive training on inclusion, diversity and monitoring regularly. While local governments add these trainings to their business plans permanently, local governments can also be audited at the national level. All local governments in the country can work in cooperation for the creation and implementation of these trainings. With an observatory to be established, the content and execution of these trainings can be supervised. Universities and administrations can carry out current works and revise the education program under the observatory in accordance with the changes that may occur in the host country, such as the current conditions and the diversity of the refugees to come.

As mentioned in the world level recommendation; the pre-tests and post-tests administered in our TAIS were on diversity and cultural diversity. In addition to this, a gender-based test can be developed to use in national scope. In the observatory which can be established, practices on gender-based questionnaires can be applied with academicians and experts on gender. Within the cooperation with local governments, before hiring social service personnel, the observatory could provide an interview tool on gender for the use of the local governments.

HOW

First of all, the training program we implement in our TAIS can be transformed into a training program that is continuously implemented by local governments. To develop this training program, a sub-unit of experts can be established in the local government under the social services unit working with forcibly displaced people. Together with the observatory to be established, this sub-unit can carry out training material development studies in constant communication. In addition to local administrations, a unit should be established in the national government in this regard. The unit to be established at the headquarters can undertake the task of both supervising local governments and developing the contents by following the developments on an international scale. The Observatory can regularly engage with local authorities on issues of forcibly displaced people, women and girls, and gender issues. It can provide training and mentorship to local government employees on this subject. In addition, it can undertake the task of observing the trainings to be implemented by local governments. In addition to the trainings, the threats and obstacles faced by the employees are of great importance in shaping the trainings. A meeting can be held regularly throughout Turkey for local government social workers to share their experiences. Although social workers may seem to be the target group in the trainings to be provided, in fact, the forcibly displaced women and girls themselves are indirectly the target group as well. For this reason, the feedback and opinions of refugees is crucial in the structure that will be formed with the cooperation of the national government, local government and universities. The observatory to be established in this regard can conduct interviews with refugees and provide information for local governments to revise their educational content.

Local service providers should improve monitoring tools adopting different data collecting techniques to identify specific needs and challenges of highly vulnerable groups

WHY

Quality and capacity of services provided by the institutions and organisations depend on the aggregated and up to date data on the specific needs and challenges of specific social groups. Depending on the culture and VC of a country, certain social groups might not be able to provide necessary feedback to institutions which might help them improve the quality and capacity of their services. Therefore, certain social groups among FDPs can be considered as “highly vulnerable” and need tailored attention and inclusion strategies while providing social services. This situation necessitates adopting an inclusive and diverse monitoring method as well as well-trained social workers who are qualified to execute the monitoring work. In addition, it is observed that negative attitudes towards FDPs increase in the host society and social service workers, especially in countries where the FDP population is dense. For this reason, host community and social workers may intentionally or unintentionally discriminate against FDPs. For this reason, it is aimed to remind that the situation of FDPs still maintains their vulnerability and to provide attitudinal change in social workers through these training sessions.

WHAT

Because the elastic nature of vulnerability context allows it to vary through time and territories, social service providers, local authorities and policy makers need to improve their monitoring methods and tools adopting an

inclusive and diverse perspective. Moreover, data collected through the monitoring work should be regularly updated. Also, the knowledge, skills and attitudes of social workers and researchers needs to be assessed and evaluated considering key elements such as inclusion, diversity and qualification on the execution of monitoring. And this monitoring should be audited by a supervisory board and should be on an international level. Because good practices in different regions will improve existing systems.

HOW

During the implementation of Turkish TAIS, 3 major trainings were provided to local social workers; inclusion training, diversity training and monitoring training. Also a pre-test / post-test method was used in order to evaluate the improvement in their knowledge, skills and attitudes. The results reveal that the combination of having awareness on inclusion/diversity and different data collecting techniques (interview, environmental scanning, questionnaire etc.) improves the quality and scale of the collected data which eventually provides a wider perspective for local authorities to benefit while tailoring their social services. Combining theoretical and practical methods offers an effective environment for social workers to adopt an inclusive and diverse monitoring work. Experience sharing meetings held annually by social workers in different countries under the supervision of an international supervisory board will ensure that existing services are regularly improved.

Create a social workers' needs-map, as drawn from their inspection with FDPs

WHY

Especially countries with large immigrant populations should develop practices that will include all FDPs but also meet their specific needs. In order to break the polarized atmosphere caused by the intense FDP population, the training sessions which will be held regularly are very important for social workers, who play a critical role in meeting the needs of FDPs, both for women and girls who have difficulties with daily social life practices. For this reason, the training of service providers in developing countries is of vital importance. As a result of the training of social workers, a needs map can also be drawn from their inspection with FDPs.

With the monitoring tool and training sessions, service providers can obtain more information about HVGs and develop their implementations. Especially in less developed countries, it can't be mentioned about equality before the law and/or in micro and meso level discrimination can be seen. So, with in-depth interviews between FDPs and service providers, detailed data can be obtained and tailored strategies can be developed. Especially in patriarchal societies, women and girls have very limited access to social life. For this reason, they cannot access the services and training provided by the government or NGOs because they are seen as a domestic service force. For this reason, women and girls are among the highly vulnerable groups. If the services cannot reach the target audience directly, the awareness of the service providers should be increased.

WHAT

Training social workers and adapting good practices in other countries to their own countries will enable the development of existing services. However, since each

country has its own context of vulnerability, an international supervisory board should be established in order to prevent possible discrimination. As a result of these meetings, which will be held annually by social workers, each country can draw up a tailored needs map for its own FDPs, taking into account the good practices in different countries. Thus, more comprehensive studies will be carried out for women and girls whose social lives are limited to the home and family, and most importantly, the awareness of social workers in this regard will be increased. The first step for the creation of the needs map is the creation of the website. The second stage is the establishment of an association in which both experts working with vulnerable groups and representatives of vulnerable groups take part in its management.

HOW

In the beginning, service providers should be trained about inclusion and diversity to implement the tool effectively. Because having an egalitarian perspective is vital. Then the service providers should be informed about the training sessions. Because without an egalitarian perspective, the trainings cannot serve the purpose. Besides, a supervisory board can be established to examine and analyse the service providers' communications with FDPs. The supervisory board should consist of the developers of this tool and/or people with experience in this field. And also municipalities and NGOs should be encouraged to support this work. Because providing the necessary funds and personnel support for the realization of the proposal is vital.

Yarmouk University, JORDAN

Psychosocial Refugee Support Forum (PRSF)

The Jordan TAIS, Psychosocial Refugee Support Forum (PRSF), has been developed to spread awareness about asylum seekers psychological and social support, reflects the social responsibility for supporting the needs of asylum seekers in terms of mental health and psychological aid. The main goal of this program is to enable asylum seekers to be self-reliant, independent, and with a little or no need for external support. To achieve such goal, asylum seekers must convert their negative experiences into a motivation that support their future life. Early identification of psychological distress and trauma, and effective care is essential in discovering the strengths that asylum seekers could rely-on to face their daily challenges and benefit from existing opportunities.

PRSF has been designed to deliver various services that contribute to minimize the effects of psychological and social challenges. These services include psychological services, social support, family services, healthcare access, economic support, and legislative support. They would contribute to improve the asylum seekers' lifestyle and enable them to integrate in the host community.

Treating mental illness for vulnerable displaced persons is not always easy. In most cases, the patient is bored of frequent visits to the mental clinic. So, the need to provide psychological support via the Internet to help with treatment without shame or exorbitant costs for each session. Moreover, psychological treatment services are considered a stigma among refugees and the host community. In addition, there is a need to sustain these services due to their importance in the personal and community level. Therefore, many vulnerable displaced persons reject these services for fear of societal stigma. Therefore, we find that many might prefer to obtain the PSS service secretly without anyone's knowledge or interference. Online system "Refugee Psychological Support System (RPSS) were developed to go upon these problems.

RPSS aims to provide assistance to those who need it on a psychological and social basis. Communicating electronically with psychological support providers and organizations that provide this service will assure individual safety. RPSS aims to provide protection, psychological and social support to treat disorders without the need for medical intervention.

Jordanian TAIS Testimonies <https://raisd-h2020.eu/research/aru/jordan/>

Jordanian Good Practices <https://raisd-h2020.eu/media/d5.1-potential-qps-jo.pdf>

Recommendations to improve policies and practices regarding the care of vulnerable groups

In light of the increase in the number of refugees and displaced persons, the basic services should be provided to them in a fair manner. It is assumed that a national framework should be created specialized in following up the programs and services provided to vulnerable groups. One of its tasks is to follow up on the services provided in various institutions, whether governmental or non-governmental, or various international organizations in order to distribute these services according to specializations and areas of interest. It can also be recommended to make a database that includes many psychological tests and psychological assessment tools in proportion to the different groups of the vulnerable, because some tools may be suitable for females and not suitable for males, or they may fit the stage of late adolescence and early adulthood groups. It can also be recommended to expand the framework of services to include children and adolescents and not be limited to those over 18 years old. Recommend expanding the topics on which training is provided to refugees in the light of the disclosure of the health, legal, psychological, family, economic, social, academic and other services aimed at empowering the vulnerable in those areas. In addition, in the light of the results of the research conducted after the implementation of the five training programmes, a number of recommendations were reached: the adoption of the programme used (health empowerment programme, legal empowerment programme, psychological empowerment programme, family empowerment programme and economic empowerment programme) within the services provided to refugees, as the results of the studies showed the effectiveness of these programmes in raising the level of health, legal, psychological, family empowerment and economic empowerment. Training of health-care providers in the programme can also be recommended. Work to develop programmes in line with the psychological services provided to refugees.

In light of the discontinuation of some services provided to the vulnerable under the Corona pandemic, it is important to take into account the importance of establishing an e-platform to provide psychosocial support services to the vulnerable and to be built on scientific grounds and supervised by specialists to verify the quality of services provided to this group in accordance with their needs and the culture of society within the framework of privacy and confidentiality.

Extending the innovative attention and inclusion strategy to other Vulnerable Groups and different Vulnerability Context

Current training programmes (health empowerment programme, legal empowerment programme, psychological empowerment programme, family empowerment programme and economic empowerment programme) for vulnerable groups with their various services and sessions are a key source of empowerment, making groups vulnerable to a number of activities that will reduce pressures that may adversely affect their lives, enable them to cope with different difficulties, and are able to choose the right strategies and ways to cope with these difficulties, making them more healthy. Psychological.

In the light of the various surveys carried out while working to identify the needs of vulnerable groups, they were found to be more likely to develop mental disorders, suffering from these psychological problems at higher rates than others, compared to those of their age, as a result of which they were subjected to various psychological, financial and social pressures, such as the difficulty of balancing their different needs with those of their family members such as school needs and social relations, and concern for the future.

Because of the seriousness of both stress and mental disorders on vulnerable groups, appropriate strategies must be sought to broaden attention and to seek strategies to integrate such groups into society. This is through awareness and education lectures in the various areas of health, legal, psychological, family, economic, social, academic and life skills training that will raise the level of health, legal, psychological, family, economic, social and academic empowerment to reach psychological well-being, so that they are better able

to meet the demands of life, conformity with oneself and conformity with others and reduce the chances of experiencing psychological disorders.

To expand the scope of services, a number of psychological measures, such as depression, anxiety and stress (DASS-21) are expected to be applied to measure mental health status, psychological resilience, irrational thought scale, self-acceptance scale, adapted to the Jordanian environment and the vulnerable living in them through the use of electronic links, to ensure access to as many of these groups as possible, especially since some of them live in remote areas of Jordan and do not have the material means to move to these services. In addition, the application is assumed to different age groups of vulnerable persons and after the number of individuals in need of assistance who receive low levels is limited to the previous scale, taking into account the distribution and provision of services in some cases independently for both males and females according to age groups and in line with the philosophy of customs and traditions prevailing in society, which limits the possibility of both males and females expressing their needs to the other sex according to their representation in the vulnerable community. Geographical distribution should also be taken into account and remote and disadvantaged areas taken into account.

The framework of services can also be expanded by: disseminating programmes to organizations and centres concerned with dealing with such groups and training their staff on such programmes so that they can be used to deal with as many different problems as possible facing vulnerable groups.

Potential adopters of the TAIS methodology, materials, products, services

Building training programmes on a well-adopted and well-established scientific basis and in various areas of health, legal, psychological, family, economic, social and academic empowerment is a new addition to the knowledge accumulation in the field of psychosocial support services for vulnerable groups, which are most needed to be aware and alert to their internal feelings and emotions. The programme can therefore be utilized and accommodated in organizations and centres concerned with the provision of psychosocial support services to vulnerable groups, and programmes can be accommodated in the department of guidance and educational psychology so that students can apply programmes during their applications for field training courses, and given the positive results of the programmes applied and their proven effectiveness in raising levels of health, legal, psychological, family and economic empowerment among vulnerable groups, and it is possible to work to pass on the experience to vulnerable members of the community. There are specialized centres that train community members on different topics, which will spread interest and transfer experience to others.

This proposal is reinforced by the fact that the construction of the training material was carried out through a survey of the needs of vulnerable groups and the opinions of specialists and experts possible to work with them in various centres and organizations dealing with the provision of various services to the vulnerable group. ARUs has been instrumental in developing the basic lines of programs and proposing activities and applying them experimentally within their different workplaces to verify their effectiveness and modify them in light of the feedback resulting from the application process to the final form of the programs that are on it. The programs also allow for modification in the light of future needs disclosed.

Activate international legislation to provide psychosocial support services, considering mental health issues related to family disintegration resulting from dispersion same family members in several countries

WHY

Because trainers and trainees often have racial biases, qualitative orientations, limited self-awareness, and a lack of knowledge about multicultural training, it must be borne in mind that when individuals from vulnerable groups and trainers in different countries come from diverse cultural and ethnic backgrounds, they bring with them their culturally conditional attitudes and beliefs to each other, which can be positive or negative, but the risk is to hinder growth and communication within the training process in the event of disagreement or bad Understanding on both sides as a result of lack of experience in the practice of multiculturalism. Therefore, the moral responsibility to practice and address cultural aspects within training is an important and necessary component for those prepared for training and training programmes. Therefore, in training, gender, age, race, religion, ability, class, culture, education and spirituality must be taken into account in an attempt to guide trainers to understand the extent of differences, prejudices and cultural aspects that constitute conflicting values of relationships in life, training and guidance.

WHAT

There are many justifications that can be referred to provide these improvements, the most important of which are cultural differences between communities that place restrictions in the process of interaction in vulnerable groups, where it was noted during the implementation of programs that some topics such as health empowerment can talk about members of vulnerable groups about the health problems they suffer from if they are general while refraining from talking about some of their problems such as skin diseases that are hindering the interaction of the vulnerable individual with Others consider that it will be seen as a stigma and therefore become the interaction of others with this individual who suffers from it cautiously for fear of transmitting to them, as well as the problems of impotence in males among the special problems, especially since the programs were required to provide services to both sexes and many other health problems. This applies to some family problems that are difficult to disclose to the opposite sex, namely domestic violence,

and to hold the male or female responsible, where differences of views have sometimes emerged between vulnerable groups, which they want to limit the possibility of interaction within the group, and therefore the provision of services on this side to both sexes is seen independently as potentially more effective given its specificity of culture in this aspect.

HOW

To work to improve these procedures, an institutional framework must be provided on which a group of experts in various fields of health, psychological, family, legal and economic must be provided based on the needs of vulnerable groups because satisfying basic psychological needs is an important requirement for the proper development of the individual. The degree of differences in society varies to the degree of association with its cultures and habits of satisfying the psychological needs of individuals, by varying factors such as age, sex, individual culture and degree of self-esteem, and this helps it to ensure an appropriate degree of harmony and psychological and social harmony, making the behaviours of the vulnerable individual more acceptable in the host society. It is recommended to provide a legal office to follow up on legal cases of vulnerable groups within international organizations in societies. There is a need to survey needs of vulnerable groups by applying specially designed measurement and testing tools for this category and by verifying the psychometry characteristics of these tools so that they are far from biased and as close as they are to objectivity; to develop current programmes that include health, legal, psychological, family and economic empowerment in proportion to needs of vulnerable groups in different countries; to work to expand the service framework to include different age groups, as children and adolescents. Taking into account multiculturalism and different cultural environments that prevent mixing between the sexes, through which the specificity of certain problems is taken into account by members of both sexes; to diversify activities so that there are many alternative exercises that can be used as needed so that the dominant character of the program becomes practical rather than theoretical.

YU recommends to Jordanian Country level (government, regional, local authorities and institutions).

Coordinate with various services providers segments to guarantee access to as many vulnerable groups as possible

WHY

The absence of relevant national programmes to provide psychosocial, legal and economic support services urges the state to rely on international programmes implemented by international and local partner institutions as they do not take into account the privacy of host Jordanian society, which limits the chances of integrating vulnerable groups into society to alleviate the isolation of some of these groups. This also limits the identification of the actual needs of vulnerable groups to integrate them into the host community to include psychological, academic, social and political development aspects, with the aim of designing national programmes consistent with the actual needs of vulnerable groups.

Because empowerment of vulnerable groups is based on several basic principles, the most important of which is for the individual to choose his own goals, take initiative and authority to make decisions, consider his or her issues and problems and the ways he or she will use to solve these issues and problems, successes and failures are seen as opportunities for learning and capacity-building, the discovery and fortification of the individual's internal elements and forces, and the individual is asked to participate in the problem-solving process to enhance his sense of responsibility, and improvements in support networks to improve problem-solving, raise and strengthen motivation to improve individual conditions. These principles are based on the individual; the role of supporters, whether they are experts, bosses at work, colleagues, family, friends, is to urge the individual to generate the energy that originates from within him, and to improve the surrounding environment. National programmes must therefore be developed in accordance with and in partnership with the needs of vulnerable groups.

WHAT

To empower vulnerable groups, it must be borne in mind that there are five levels of empowerment: first: well-being; this level focuses on material well-being in various areas of life, such as: food level, income level, level of education and health level, in order to meet the material needs of the individual, and this level deals with individuals as a social group with material needs that

need to be satisfied, by identifying the means available to reach this, so that these material needs must be satisfied with the individual. This aspect is not focused on by many training programs, but can take care of some aspects and leave others.

Secondly, the possibility; this level aims to invest opportunities and resources in raising the capacity of the individual to achieve equal opportunities. Third: awareness; this level focuses on raising the capacity of individuals to critically and consciously analyse the prevailing systems of discrimination against individuals and the erroneous social practices that lead to their continuation. Fourth: participation; specifically, active positive participation in the decision-making process, so that the individual has a positive role in the decision-making process, and traditional society finds it difficult to apply this form of participation, and the process of increasing participation of individuals represents a potential contribution to raising levels of empowerment. Fifth: The ability to act means the ability of individuals to improve their standard of living, ensure equal participation, strengthen the role of individuals in controlling decision-making appropriate to their social lives, and empowerment may be at the level of organizations or societies.

HOW

The need to provide a more comprehensive mechanism for conducting surveys of the needs of vulnerable groups based on more comprehensive national policies such as work on programmes in social empowerment, political empowerment, empowerment for people with special needs and empowerment in parental care, particularly support and training for adolescent mothers from vulnerable groups. Work is needed to formulate an academic empowerment program to work on literacy among vulnerable groups. The CORONA pandemic affected many vulnerable groups and reduced their access to psychological, academic and health services, which negatively affected the psychological state of vulnerable groups. Therefore, we must work to increase the efficiency of workers in providing services to vulnerable groups within the framework of specialization and skill and not to leave the field in general to all intruders in the psychological professions.

YU recommends to Jordanian Host community level (ARU members/inclusion strategy implementers)

Involve members of the host Jordanian community in the preparation of support programs and allow community groups access psychological support services too

WHY

In order to achieve social justice and reduce the level of negative sentiment towards refugees and displaced persons, where there is sometimes a negative view towards them, especially since some consider them partners with different resources and their presence has contributed to raising the rate of wages for homes and reducing the level of wages of work where individuals from vulnerable groups accept much lower wages than some jobs deserve, this drives more negative feelings and limits the possibility of integrating vulnerable groups into the host society.

WHAT

With the large influx of refugees in Jordan, employers are noticing that Jordanian labour is laid off and tyrannical to

other vulnerable groups due to low wages and more working hours. There has also been an increase in the number of separations between community members and refugee marriages, often causing negative feelings towards them.

HOW

Raising community awareness of refugees' legal, health, academic and other rights through traditional media and social media and holding training courses for couples to help them achieve family consensus that will be reflected in the community. Work to monitor employers more effectively while taking into account the importance of proportional representation of the two years within establishments

Raise awareness of vulnerable groups in sources of health, psychological and legal care provided by organizations and bodies working in the host community.

WHY

So that the need of these vulnerable groups is not exploited, employed at low wages and spent some money to access health care and not a source of exploitation by some who promise to complete some of their own transactions such as accommodation or employment opportunities determined by the laws of the host country and regulated and impenetrable. This is what the programmes that have been developed are provided, which aim to empower refugees with legal, health, psychological and economic aspects that they like to help integrate them into the host community.

WHAT

The exploitation of refugees and displaced persons in the host community and refugees themselves is noted, so refugees must be made aware of the camps and their

whereabouts while providing psychological and community support through awareness and education by training them to coexist within difficult economic conditions and how to adapt to developments and adapt to a vulnerable environment.

HOW

Educational lectures are held for all vulnerable groups to publicize their rights and duties and limit the provision of training programmes and psychological services to groups that prove their need for such services and those who receive low grades on the standards used, in light of which refugees are divided into segments that share these needs, which is more beneficial as each program includes a homogeneous group in terms of needs, age groups and gender.

Lebanese International University, LEBANON

Health 4 SEAD “Health, Social Emotional, Academic, Development”

After conducting interviews with 5 experts and 27 vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced, representing the quintuple helix of RRI, and given the current circumstances of the pandemic of COVID-19, LIU adapted its TAIS ideas and adapted its actions to meet the current needs of vulnerable people. LIU undertook three pilot studies/ stages with pre, through and post based on the stakeholder's outcomes. Actually, stakeholders included, though not limited to, LIU Health Committee, Policy makers, Research community, Education community, Business and Industry, and Society organization.

In Lebanon, the designed TAIS is geared at addressing social, emotional, and academic problems. The program had a positive impact on the Syrian people in camps in addition to delivering a holistic Corona Virus awareness to children, pregnant women, elderly people, malnourished people, and people who are ill or immune-compromised. RAISD team in Lebanon, through its Health committee worked to enrich all stakeholders with the coping tools needed to raise their awareness and minimize challenges and trauma they were and continue to face amidst and beyond the COVID 19 pandemic and the dire economic situation and plethora of crises in Lebanon which has had also difficult hardships visited upon Syrian refugees and vulnerable people.

The aim of the TAIS was to deliver an online awareness campaign, called Health 4 SEAD “Health, Social Emotional, Academic, Development”. H 4 SEAD geared to engage in COVID-19 awareness, prevention and treatment information campaigns through on line dissemination, but not limited to, community groups and religious leaders, telephone hotlines, flyers, posters, bulk SMS and WhatsApp messaging, radio announcements, focus group discussions, leaflets, billboards and mural drawings. broadcasted videos, brochures with instructions.

The outcome of this pilot project aimed at empowering a strong pool of NGOs and Information Focal Point networks all over Lebanon in preparing them to facilitate and support their teaching efforts of Syrian, Palestinian and displaced people in refugee camps. This was done through LIU health Committee's active participation and sharing of practical experiences utilizing online means. The program focused on different skills and capacities (digital, emotional, communication, leadership, management and entrepreneurship) that were selected to form part of the program, then validated and highlighted by ARU members and some potential beneficiaries in the consultation processes. These skills also stood out for having a high value benefit for the job market, and professional and personal development of the beneficiaries.

Lebanese TAIS Testimonies <https://raisd-h2020.eu/research/aru/lebanon/>

Lebanese Good Practices <https://raisd-h2020.eu/media/d5.1-potential-gps-lb.pdf>

Recommendations to improve policies and practices regarding the care of vulnerable groups

At the Lebanese national government level, The RAISD project recommends that: refugees and Forcibly Displaced People (FDP) have a right to education, but not all education offered is suitable for them. The government gives priority to the planning of adequate measures to ensure that access to education is available for FDP and refugees pending the possibility of a durable solution of either voluntary repatriation or local integration. Respect existing obligations for the provision of education for FDP and refugees within the human rights framework and as indicated by UNHCR and other international guidelines. This means making greater efforts to facilitate the provision of further education and vocational training for FDP and refugee children into the education system of the host country as in the case of Lebanon.

Quite often, FDP arrive in host countries having missed parts of their education due to war and conflict and face difficulty continuing their education. Digital learning and innovation hubs for learning can be considered as a way of giving young refugees, host communities, and teachers access to the internet and digital learning materials. The aim of such hubs should address common challenges in education such as limited infrastructure and learning materials, high student-teacher ratios, access to education, and high dropout rates.

Crucially, young girls face different sets of vulnerabilities and challenges in accessing education, which include early marriage, distance from schools, and priorities of education to boys. Such challenges discourage them from accessing or continuing education. Within Lebanon, there is evidence of decreased school enrolment of forcibly displaced girls post-COVID-19, which has exacerbated the challenges of an already complicated environment.

Governments must recognise the need to consider and incorporate this aspect within national education planning in order to facilitate equitable access for refugee girls and boys.

The COVID pandemic has underscored the critical importance of reliable data when addressing the needs of FDP and other vulnerable groups. It is clear that more and better socioeconomic data as well as rigorous analysis of that data is required to better inform the design of policies and interventions. Data deficiencies are particularly acute for FDP and vulnerable groups facing challenges in areas such as health care, employment, and education.

Lebanon is a country hit by a deep economic and social crisis, compounded by COVID and the port of Beirut explosion in August 2020, is suffering from an even more dramatic impact. In that, more than a million among those forcibly displaced have been driven into poverty in the immediate aftermath of the COVID-19 crisis in Lebanon. By April 2020, 60 percent of Syrian refugees had been permanently laid off and 31 percent temporarily lost their jobs whereas the figures for Lebanese workers were 39 and 38 percent respectively. And recently updated figures for Lebanon indicate that by the end of 2021 an additional 2.5 million Lebanese individuals and 430,000 Syrian (World Bank-UNHCR, 2021).

Extending the innovative attention and inclusion strategy to other Vulnerable Groups and different Vulnerability

Context

LIU's TAIS focused on enhancing Higher Education students' competence level in leadership, digital media and communication through the medium of the English language. It has been noted that such students became better with the new tools which improved their communication with others especially at LIU. The primary objective of TAIS was centred around improving and empowering students for the working place, to enrich their employment status or dissemination to develop awareness in Syrian camps and schools they teach in. As a result of the unprecedented COVID-19 pandemic and political upheavals in Lebanon, modifications of TAIS had to be made as a consequence of both the micro- level and macro- level disputes. It should be noted that the pandemic resulted in serious consequences at the health, social and political level. The implementation of digital device training in the digital literacies of the students imply a success in knowing how strong these students have improved at the meso and macro levels.

Potential adopters of the TAIS methodology, materials, products, services

The outcome of TAIS at LIU suggests that Education of forcibly displaced people and refugees should have the EU institutions and agencies Enter into partnership agreements with the UNHCR, UNICEF and WHO to tackle the problems of refugees and forcibly displaced persons in host countries on the educational, political, social and health levels.

TAIS should, however, be paid to the very differing conditions of refugees and FDP in Lebanon. In that there are many organizations and agencies, such as UNHCR, which are focused on dealing with refugees and FDP in a professional and expert manner; in many cases NGOs and governmental bodies act on site in local or regional contexts. However, not all experience and expertise can be transferred from one focus of action to another.

Foster co-ordination between host government and local community, governmental organizations and NGOs working with refugees and FDP

WHY

In Lebanon, the situation of refugees and Forcibly Displaced People (FDP) must be resolved either by return, integration in the host country or resettlement in a third country. Pending decisions on which course to take, educational provisions must be made for each eventuality. Education is not only a basic right but also vital and essential for both FDP and refugees. Depending on age so too is vocational education and training. What is at stake is their preparation for life and for employment. This is relevant for all persons in such position.

Co-ordination is necessary between the host government and local community, governmental organizations (such as the United Nations High Commission for Refugees (UNHCR) and UNICEF) and NGOs working with refugees and FDP. Considerable resources and sustained commitment by governments and donors are necessary for the education of FDP and refugees. More effective intervention at an early stage can reduce long-term costs.

Education should support active participation of FDP and other vulnerable groups in the agenda of their community. Inclusion and the sense of ownership must not be postponed until all problems are solved, but the solutions of problems (e.g. of sociability and community building) should be fostered and assessed under the circumstances of FDP and refugee education.

WHAT

Given the fact that no education policy can be developed by itself, education is always embedded in a network of social, political and cultural structures, which are – under the circumstances of emergency – very hard to streamline and organize. Instead of pushing education down the priority ladder, it should always be included in the main actions of the vanguard, policies and actions geared for FDP and how they are conducted.

As of September 2021, and due to the ongoing economic and social crisis hitting Lebanon, almost three-quarter of the population including Syrian refugees live in poverty according to UN Economic and Social Commission for West Asia.

Forcibly displaced people rely disproportionately on international and humanitarian assistance, especially during crises such as the current economic collapse in Lebanon. In line with international refugee policy, the Lebanese government is unable to provide the same educational services for refugee children as nationals within schools.

One of the key and persistent challenges in refugee's access to education in Lebanon is language - especially amongst Syrian refugees trying to assimilate within the Lebanese national education system, where the language of instruction is English.

HOW

How should countries respond to some of the unique challenges faced by refugee children - particularly girls - in accessing and continuing their education?

The right to education should not be restricted to primary education. All age groups and types of FDP should be supplied with a maximum of educational care. Although not only targeted at FDP, alternative education pathways offer important lessons that could be incorporated within the national education frameworks in other countries and could be adapted for the specific vulnerabilities of refugee children in accessing education. FDP and refugees require, in addition to the normal education, specific mental care, cultural orientation and language training. This needs skilled and trained teachers with the proper material.

This can be addressed by recruiting refugee teachers who are able to assist in language bridging within the refugee camps and settlements. These refugee teachers can be highly valuable assets in their role acting as educators for the majority of the refugee learners.

LIU recommends to Lebanese Country level (government, regional, local authorities and institutions).

Migrant integration policies should be designed to fill the gap between government's ministries and agencies

WHY

At national and regional level, migrant integration policies are often designed and executed leaving a gap between the government's ministries and agencies.

Therefore, some of the policies and strategies are very far from each other. There are gaps in the programs and repetitive mistakes with hardly any coordination. Instead a collaborative approach should be adopted. Moreover, while some host countries have been able to introduce ad hoc coping mechanisms and policies for FDP and other vulnerable groups, those forcibly displaced are often excluded from recovery measures implemented by the Lebanese governments.

Based on surveys and research thus far done, TAIS found that FDP in Lebanon have suffered setbacks in health access, education and food security, while also noting severe losses in employment and income. For example, financial constraints were often the biggest barriers to accessing food resulting in severe food insecurity. The results in most cases were often worse for those forcibly displaced compared to their hosts.

For humanitarian and development policy, inclusion of FDPs should be more augmented despite the technical and financial challenge it poses over their regular approaches to gathering population statistics. Targeted support and capacity building from the humanitarian and international agencies need to work closely with national statistical offices which will allow for greater visibility of FDPs.

Moreover, important insights could be gained by further pursuing research on points such as: the degree to which initial socioeconomic conditions are associated with FDP and host outcomes and convergence, exploration of the explanatory factors and variation in policies implemented at the national level, the extent in which FDPs were included or excluded, and how humanitarian actors filled existing operational and policy gaps and where have they successfully boosted the national response.

Equally, it would be useful to understand the cross-cutting barriers for all the forcibly displaced, such as

being in possession of the necessary personal documents to access services and protection.

Furthermore, there are important openings for research to explore the underlying factors and examining the causes of relatively greater employment loss among the FDP compared to the host population and in determining the lessons that can be drawn from the challenges around securing access to employment and education.

WHAT

As with so many dimensions of well-being, lack of financial resources is a consistent barrier to accessing health care among host and refugees who need care but are unlikely to receive it. Both refugee and national households in Lebanon report that financial constraints were the biggest reason for not getting medical services when needed, followed by the lack of available medical staff.

Mental health concerns among the displaced have been observed anecdotally by those working with displaced populations during the pandemic, but it has been difficult to measure systematically.

The reasons for the observed food insecurity are varied, but for those surveyed by TAIS, financial constraints are among the top two reasons given.

HOW

This can be done in collaboration with national statistical offices to build sustainable capacity. Inclusion of the FDP and other vulnerable groups in national data collection practices allow for these populations' integration into policy responses as well as humanitarian and development interventions.

The living conditions of FDP and other vulnerable groups have been poorly documented due to a lack of more inclusive and reliable data. Nonetheless, the limited available evidence indicates the importance of a deeper understanding of these vulnerable populations.

Evidence from the TAIS surveys indicate that most of the FDP experienced employment losses which have aggravated the socioeconomic conditions of both those forcibly displaced and their hosts. The loss of income is a significant risk for FDPs and hosts that can cascade to create or exacerbate additional welfare challenges, with consequences on their poverty levels.

FDP and other vulnerable groups should be empowered to express their perspectives and aspirations

WHY

Looking beyond the current situation, the full socioeconomic repercussions will play out over the medium- to long-term. This highlights the need for better tracking mechanisms that collect regular and reliable data on vulnerable groups to inform more comprehensive approaches to alleviate their plight. In most countries affected by forced displacement, FDP are rarely represented in national statistics. This is frequently due to a variety of capacity reasons impeding national statistical offices from addressing vulnerable groups through their regular work.

The RAISD project recommends that FDP and other vulnerable groups should be empowered to express their perspectives and aspirations. Education should lead them into an active life without complacency. Girls and women should be given special attention since traditionally men have been the dominant group in gender relations. People with direct scars and wounds from their refugee experience and displacement should be given special empowerment and capacities should be supported.

WHAT

Respect for the other is an important goal despite the shared fates among coping individuals that there is no one-way pattern of communication among the group. It is necessary to know and to learn about the recent histories of the members of a community, and it is necessary to establish respectful communication between the FDP and other vulnerable groups with their counterparts from government, supervising and organizing agencies and supporters.

The curriculum for FDP and refugee education in all its various aspects must follow one crucial goal: it must pave the way for them to regain control of their lives in the most practical sense. Learning must open the path to overcome victimization. Therefore, practical skills of direct relevance to the given circumstances take priority over knowledge acquisition.

The learning process and procedures of learning should be given priority over an ideal and balanced curriculum. Learner-centered methods and approaches should be at the center of all attempts. Since relevance is the main criterion for FDP in refugee education, the learner in his/her present circumstances has to be in the center of educational goals and procedures. Determining what is relevant to the specific group of FDP and refugees has to become part of the educational process and a way of rebuilding confidence in the learners' own strength. Because many refugees and FDP suffer from traumas and other grave learning problems and challenges, tailored approach should be developed.

HOW

External factors (such as international agencies, intergovernmental and governmental organizations, NGOs etc.) must also reflect their own role in all activities. The way external actors are perceived by vulnerable groups has increasingly gained importance. The conduct of the external actors is as decisive on the inclination of the FDP orientation as the policies of their own peers and the attractors or repellents from their home country.

Government funding and humanitarian assistance should be channelled into reinforcing the formal education system to guarantee FDP access to education

WHY

The adoption of legal and policy frameworks is not enough to uphold the right to education for FDP in Lebanon. Challenges to implementing these policies are linked to institutional, financial, political, and cultural factors. While most policies assign government sectors to take a lead role in assisting and protecting FDP, these bodies are frequently underfunded and lack clear lines of authority. The need to include internally displaced children in planning and decision-making processes is a common aspect of these policies.

However, due to FDPs' lack of representative bodies in many contexts, such involvement does not always materialise. Most of the policies have some provisions around age, gender and diversity, resulting in inadequate responses to convergent vulnerabilities. Lebanon must acknowledge such vulnerabilities and shape their planning and implementation efforts in a convergent fashion.

The existence of international standards such as the Guiding Principles has accelerated efforts by countries to ensure FDPs' rights are not only included in legal policy frameworks but are also practically recognised through their effective inclusion in national services and participation in decision-making. Nonetheless, while those instruments may speak of a strong political will, wide gaps between policies and practice remain.

International actors that support drafting FDP policies should sustain their support through efforts to ensure that Lebanon's capacities are strengthened. Government funding and humanitarian assistance should be channelled into reinforcing the formal education system to guarantee FDP access to education.

Inclusion of FDP into the national education system can lead to greater integration with host communities. However, development of legal frameworks does not automatically constitute the fulfilment of the right to education due to issues with implementation and other barriers to education. In Lebanon, internally displaced children's direct inclusion in the national

education system yielded positive integration results for IDPs with host communities.

However, given the breakdown of community, family and other social support structures and challenges for sustainable economic and livelihood activities, mental healthcare interventions among IDPs should also focus

WHAT

Accurate data on the education needs and provision for internally displaced children is poor. The majority of forcibly displaced children are not included in national data collection. Data is vital for policymaking, budgeting, implementation of educational services, and to accountability. At a minimum, data must be disaggregated by gender, age and disability.

The pandemic has resulted in additional funding challenges for governments, as they work to meet safe back to school requirements. For countries hosting FDP, this means more pressure on already overstretched education systems.

A greater coordinated effort is required from the international community to strengthen the global education architecture and funding.

Children often account for large proportions of forcibly displaced populations and face unique challenges to access education in host countries and/or communities. Education in displacement is not only a basic human right but a crucial part of durable solutions to displacement that provides refugee and/or returnee children with the tools and support they need to complete their education based on their previous experiences.

What FDP and refugees in Lebanon have in common is a wide variety of individual experience: traumatic memories of recent violence, loss of family members, rape, destruction of property, deprivation, and individual and group humiliation.

HOW

This can be done through further collaborative research across disciplines, methodological approaches, and the health and protection sectors, in order to tackle the complex challenges for improving FDP health.

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